

Toward Foundational Models for Knapsack Problems

Thomas Asikis*, Debasmita Dutta*, and Lucas Böttcher*

* Department of Computational Science and Philosophy

Frankfurt School of Finance and Management

Frankfurt, Germany

thomas@asikis.ai, debasmita.dutta@fs-students.de, l.boettcher@fs.de

Abstract—We use the term “foundational model” in combinatorial optimization to denote a neural optimization framework in which the architecture and inference procedure are grounded in optimization-theoretic principles. We study whether such models can provide bounded-inference, approximate solution mechanisms for the 0–1 knapsack problem. We argue, first, that no exact polynomial-inference foundational model can exist for the 0–1 knapsack problem, or for any other NP-hard combinatorial optimization problem, unless $P = NP$. Any model whose inference procedure is polynomially bounded is itself a polynomial-time algorithm. We argue, second, that an *approximate* foundational model is nonetheless attainable on typical-case distributions. Classical asymptotic-optimality results for generalized-greedy heuristics and probabilistic bounds for knapsack core algorithms suggest a mechanism for typical-case approximation. Under suitable random models, the linear-programming (LP) relaxation fixes most item decisions, leaving only a small residual set for refinement. We then present a deployable and fully differentiable learning encoder pipeline with a decoder refinement. The pipeline maps each item to a pair of LP-induced coordinates given by a tilted Lagrangian density, augments this representation with a higher-dimensional feature lift to address coordinate collisions, and trains a *permutation-equivariant set encoder* that predicts, in one forward pass, the kinetics (q_0, p_0, λ_0) of a *fixed symplectic primal–dual flow*; a short damped leapfrog rollout transports the relaxed state toward a near-optimal vertex, and a reduced-cost core peel with a conditional-value-at-risk (CVaR) Monte-Carlo decode rounds the result. The encoder is supervised by a closed-form structural gradient whose magnitude is the per-item rank-violation gap to the LP-induced ranking, and never falls below the Dantzig floor by construction of the core peel. On the held-out Jookan benchmark (whole set, 2975 certified-optimum instances, peeled to a reduced-cost core of size $K_{\text{core}}=512$), the pipeline closes 462 instances exactly versus 104 for Dantzig, at a mean relative optimality gap of 0.143% versus 0.473%. Decoding runs at ~ 30 ms (best-of- M) to ~ 200 ms (CVaR, 8 rounds) per instance. We make no blanket wall-clock-speedup claim; on a COMBO-adversarial corpus the defensible advantage is 10^2 – $10^4\times$ on the pathological tail where the exact solver’s search explodes, while the primary, distribution-agnostic axis we report is exact closures relative to the Dantzig greedy heuristic and its MC derivatives.

Index Terms—Combinatorial optimization, neural combinatorial optimization, knapsack problem, foundational models, differentiable optimization, permutation-equivariant set encoders, Hamiltonian primal–dual flow, conditional value-at-risk decoding.

I. INTRODUCTION

COMBINATORIAL optimization is concerned with finding an optimal solution to an objective function over a discrete set of feasible points. Problems of this kind appear throughout computer science and operations research [1], [2],

in applications as varied as circuit design, facility location, job scheduling, and vehicle routing. Many of them are NP-hard [3], so unless $P = NP$ no polynomial-time algorithm can solve them exactly. Modern deep-learning pipelines for adjacent domains, including vision, language, and biological sequence modeling [4], [5], have reached a regime in which a single pretrained network, trained once and queried at fixed cost, generalizes across a vast space of inputs through one forward pass. It is tempting to ask the analogous question for discrete optimization. Can a single amortized network serve as a *foundational model* for an NP-hard problem, trained on a distribution of instances, then deployed to return high-quality feasible solutions in milliseconds, without invoking a combinatorial solver at inference time? The 0–1 knapsack problem is the natural testbed. It is the simplest non-trivial integer program, it underlies a large fraction of practical resource-allocation pipelines, and its instance space is rich enough to span the full spectrum from trivially greedy-solvable to provably hard.

The analogy with large language models is worth drawing out, because it shapes our design. A language model embeds a sequence of tokens, mixes them with attention so that each token’s representation depends on the others, and decodes the result. Our knapsack model embeds a set of items, mixes them with attention, and decodes a feasible selection. The items of an instance form an exchangeable set rather than an ordered sequence, so we replace causal self-attention by permutation-equivariant set attention, the induced set-attention block of the Set Transformer [6]. This plays the role of the encoder. In place of an autoregressive token decoder we use a short, fixed primal–dual flow followed by a Monte-Carlo rounding step, which plays the role of the decoder. The encoder is trained once on a distribution of instances and is queried at fixed cost, as in the foundational-model recipe. The combinatorial structure of the problem, not a free architectural choice, dictates the two substitutions, exchangeable-set attention in place of causal attention and a flow-plus-rounding decoder in place of an autoregressive one.

The combinatorial-optimization literature contains a substantial line of neural-network–based solvers [7]–[18]. In this work, we examine the 0–1 knapsack problem, a paradigmatic NP-hard combinatorial optimization problem. In neural approaches to this problem, strong performance has been reported on small synthetic instances [8], [11], [19], [20], whereas hard, large-scale published benchmarks [21]–[23] are often absent from evaluation. The knapsack problem admits a fully polynomial-time approximation scheme [24], showing that obtaining a

worst-case approximation guarantee is not, by itself, the central difficulty. At the same time, hard instance families are known to induce very large branch-and-bound search trees for exact solvers [25], [26]. Recent practical benchmarks also include instances requiring substantial CPU time for state-of-the-art methods [23]. This combination of approximation tractability and persistent exact-solver hardness motivates the use of the 0–1 knapsack problem to characterize when a single pretrained network can function as a foundational model for an entire NP-hard problem class.¹

1) *Why a universal neural knapsack solver is ill-posed:* The naive reading of “foundational model”, a single network that efficiently solves *every* knapsack instance, is not merely hard but ill-posed, for four reasons that compound. (i) *Complexity.* A network whose forward pass runs in time polynomial in n and is correct on every instance would decide an NP-hard problem in polynomial time; under $P \neq NP$ this is impossible, so a bounded-inference model must be approximate and must be allowed to degrade on the hard tail (Proposition 3). (ii) *No free lunch.* Averaged over all instance distributions, no inductive bias dominates: performance bought on one family is paid back on its adversarial complement, so a model tuned for one distribution is necessarily mis-specified for another. (iii) *Solver-specific hardness.* Hardness is a property of the (instance, algorithm) pair, not of the instance alone. We exhibit a corpus at $n = 1000$ engineered against one exact branch-and-bound solver: COMBO [28] requires a *median* wall time of 73 s (max 313 s), while RECORD [29] disposes of the *identical* instances in sub-millisecond time. An instance pathological for one solver is trivial for another, so there is no instance-intrinsic “hardness axis” for a universal model to learn. (iv) *The off-relaxation ceiling.* A continuous relaxation places the easy signal on the LP/Lagrangian manifold, whereas the integer optimum x^* generically lies *off* that manifold by exactly the integrality gap δ_{LP-IP} . A model that fixes a continuous energy landscape equal to the relaxation has its basin at the LP vertex \bar{x} , so x^* is, by construction, unreachable by pure descent on a fixed potential. This is a combinatorial gap, not a training artifact.

We distinguish two regimes: (i) exact worst-case solvability and (ii) approximate typical-case performance. Any model whose inference procedure runs in polynomial time is itself a polynomial-time algorithm. In the exact worst-case regime, such a model cannot solve an NP-hard problem exactly on all instances unless $P = NP$. This observation applies equally to feed-forward, recurrent, transformer, and autoregressive architectures whose total inference cost is polynomially bounded. Hard-instance generators, such as that of Jookan et al. [23], provide datasets that expose this worst-case limitation in the knapsack setting.

The typical-case regime is different. Classical asymptotic results identify conditions under which approximate foundational modeling is theoretically justified. The first is the theorem of Rinnooy Kan, Stougie, and Vercellis for the multi-

knapsack problem [30], which we restate in Section III. The second is the probabilistic analysis of 0–1 knapsack by Beier and Vöcking, who show that under random perturbations of adversarial instances, the expected number of Pareto-optimal knapsack fillings is polynomial in the number of items n and the inverse perturbation scale [31]. They also show that, for uniformly random profits and weights, the algorithmic core contains $\mathcal{O}(\log^3 n)$ items with high probability [32]. Together, these results support the view that, under these random models, the fractional linear-programming (LP) relaxation, obtained by allowing fractional item selection, already fixes most of the item-selection decisions. Only a polylogarithmic-size set of borderline items is left for a small residual search.

Based on this characterization, we develop a deployable and fully differentiable learning pipeline with a Monte-Carlo refinement. Each item is mapped to two coordinates induced by the LP relaxation. Because this projection can yield coordinate collisions, we augment it with a deterministic feature lift, that is, an augmentation into a higher-dimensional space. We train a permutation-equivariant set encoder using a closed-form structural gradient whose magnitude is the per-item rank-violation gap to the LP-induced ranking. Target-consistent rankings within the class bands lie in a zero-gradient region of the induced flow, which prevents the instability caused by the non-vanishing surrogate gradients identified by Yin et al. [33] for identity straight-through estimators. At inference time the encoder predicts the kinetics of a short primal–dual flow, and a reduced-cost peel restricts the rounding to a small residual core. We add Dantzig’s greedy heuristic [34] as a floor, so the decoded incumbent is never worse than Dantzig, and we refine inside the core by a risk-seeking Monte-Carlo decode. The refinement step is modular. We use Monte-Carlo rounding throughout, but any solver can play this role on the residual core, for example an approximate or exact dynamic program restricted to the items on which the leading candidates disagree (Appendix H-D).

Our contributions are as follows.

- 1) We formulate a foundational model for knapsack problems as an approximate, typical-case framework. Its scope is delimited on one side by the exact worst-case hardness barrier, which Proposition 3 restates in neural-architecture terms, and on the other by classical greedy-family asymptotics and smoothed core bounds [30], [31] (§IV).
- 2) We identify three types of coordinate collisions in the LP-induced item representation. We introduce a deterministic feature lift that resolves these coordinate collisions and provide an ablation across raw, projected, and lifted features to quantify the resulting discriminative gain (§VII).
- 3) We derive a closed-form structural gradient for rank-greedy selection, which we call “swap-hinge with a soft per-class band”. The LP-induced reference ranking is a zero-gradient region of the resulting gradient flow. The construction complements differentiable-ranking surrogates such as soft-rank of Blondel et al. [35], perturbed combinatorial optimizers of Berthet et al. [36], and SparseMAP of Niculae et al. [37], but is specifically designed for capacity-respecting greedy selection (§VIII).

¹We use the term foundational model in combinatorial optimization to denote a neural optimization framework in which the architecture and inference procedure are grounded in optimization-theoretic principles, distinguishing our approach from foundation models as broadly pretrained reusable models [27].

- 4) We cast the encoder as an amortized convexifier: a permutation-equivariant set encoder predicts, in one forward pass, the kinetics $(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0)$ of a Hamiltonian primal-dual flow on a fixed landscape built from the LP drift, an augmented-Lagrangian capacity term, and box/cap log-barriers. A short damped symplectic leapfrog rollout ($k_{\text{leap}} = 16$, step $h = 0.02$, contraction $\gamma = 0.97$) then transports the relaxed state \mathbf{q} toward a near-optimal vertex, with a scale-invariant KKT-residual diagnostic ρ measuring stationarity (§IX).
- 5) As an ongoing extension, we explore *learning the landscape itself*, oracle-free: a learned residual potential $\Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}(\mathbf{q}) = s_\phi \sum_i (q_i - t_i)^2$ over a learned anchor \mathbf{t} and a learned Riemannian metric M_θ that reduces to the fixed barrier-Hessian metric M at unit multipliers, paired with a deploy-time conditional-value-at-risk (CVaR) Monte-Carlo decoder restricted to the reduced-cost core. The learned basin is well-posed and generalizes on held-out data; preliminary closure results are promising and are reported in Appendix G.
- 6) We validate the pipeline on hard knapsack benchmarks: (i) the Pisinger benchmark classes [21], (ii) the corresponding extension by Smith–Miles et al. [22], and (iii) the recent adversarial generator of Jookan et al. [23]. We report both out-of-sample (OOS) and out-of-distribution (OOD) generalization. The full benchmarking framework is publicly available as part of the codebase accompanying this paper (§XI).

2) *The right object: a distributional, amortized convexifier:* We therefore reframe the goal. The deployable object is not a universal solver but a *distributional* one: a model trained per instance distribution that learns a per-instance reparameterization under which a fixed, cheap integrator lands near a high-quality integer solution for instances drawn from that distribution. In this view the encoder f_θ is an *amortized convexifier*. From the lifted features ϕ it emits, in one forward pass, the kinetics $(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0) = f_\theta(\phi)$ of a continuous flow state $\mathbf{q} \in (0, 1)^n$, together with the initial momentum \mathbf{p}_0 and dual λ_0 that steer a fixed symplectic integrator toward a near-optimal vertex; the LP optimum $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is then a single point on the trajectory rather than its terminus. This controlled-dynamics, predict-the-initial-condition-so-a-fixed-integrator-reaches-the-target viewpoint follows the amortized-inference lineage of neural control of dynamical systems [38] and permutation-equivariant set attention [6]. The honest ceiling is relocated, not removed: from “everything off the relaxation manifold is unreachable” to “everything outside the training distribution is unreachable.” This is the strongest claim compatible with $P \neq NP$ and no free lunch, and it is the claim we make. Because hardness is solver-specific, we adopt a per-solver stance in the spirit of MATILDA [22]: for each classical solver S we co-train an encoder-generator pair $(\mathcal{E}_S, \mathcal{G}_S)$, where \mathcal{G}_S learns a distribution on which S struggles and \mathcal{E}_S routes those instances to a good solution despite the structural hardness for S . This gives a constructive per-solver lower bound rather than the universal upper bound that no free lunch forbids.

We preserve a hard to solve Knapsack instance family as held-out, namely the Jookan benchmark, which contains 2975

certified-optimum instances. The deployed pipeline closes 462 instances to the integer optimum exactly versus 104 for Dantzig, at a mean relative optimality gap of 0.143% against Dantzig’s 0.473%. The decoded incumbent is *never worse than Dantzig by construction*: the reduced-cost core peel uses Dantzig’s value as a floor and the Monte-Carlo/CVaR decode keeps the best incumbent over all rounds, so the floor holds across the Monte-Carlo rounds (§IX-H, §XII). Decoding runs at ~ 30 ms (best-of- M) to ~ 200 ms (CVaR, 8 rounds) per instance. Detailed tables are in Section XI.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews related work. Section III summarizes the relevant notation and recalls the LP relaxation, the Dantzig heuristic, and the Rinnooy Kan–Stougie–Vercellis result used throughout the paper. Section IV delineates the exact worst-case hardness barrier and the regime in which an approximate foundational model is meaningful. Section V discusses the obstacles that have limited prior learning methods, and Sections VI–IX develop our pipeline. Section X describes the benchmark generators, and Section XI reports the experimental results. Section XII concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Early neural approaches to combinatorial optimization include the work of Hopfield and Tank [39], which used an analog Hopfield network to encode a traveling-salesman problem (TSP) energy landscape. Subsequent mean-field methods extended these ideas to knapsack problems [40], [41]. Smith [42] surveyed this early generation of neural optimization methods. Over the past decade, the architectures, training approaches, and benchmark scale have changed substantially. In this section, we first review prior work by training paradigm, then discuss specific work on knapsack problems, and finally summarize related work on technical tools used in our pipeline.

a) *Training paradigms:* Supervised approaches include pointer networks [43], which generate solutions autoregressively and are trained on solver-generated examples. Related supervised and generative methods include graph-convolutional networks [44] and diffusion-based solvers [16]. Reinforcement-learning approaches instead learn a construction policy from realized returns. Bello et al. [8] combined pointer networks with REINFORCE on TSP and knapsack instances with up to 200 items; Kool et al. [9] used an attention encoder; Kwon et al. [11] exploited solution symmetries; Khalil et al. [10] learned greedy construction policies using reinforcement learning and graph embeddings. A recurring issue in reinforcement-learning approaches is that sample efficiency degrades with problem size and out-of-distribution generalization remains difficult. Unsupervised approaches were also considered for combinatorial optimization problems [45]–[47]. Recent work has shown that classical greedy or local-search baselines could match or outperform several neural approaches on the problems they targeted [48]–[50].

b) *Knapsack-specific learning and benchmarks:* For knapsack specifically, Hertrich and Skutella gave analytical size bounds for recurrent networks that compute optimal or provably good solution values [51], [52]. Nomer et al. [19] applied a

sequence-to-sequence model with attention to instances with up to 200 items. Pozgaj et al. [20] revisited knapsack from the perspective of neural algorithmic reasoning, supervising intermediate dynamic-programming structure. To our knowledge, none of these prior works reported evaluation on the hard benchmark classes [21] or the recent hard-instance generator of Jookan et al. [23].

Our empirical evaluation draws on three sources of hard knapsack instances. Pisinger’s benchmark classes [21] were designed to show that the 0–1 knapsack problem remains hard for exact algorithms despite decades of progress on standard instances. Smith–Miles, Christiansen, and Muñoz [22] revisited this question through instance-space analysis and the MATILDA platform [53]. Jookan, Leyman, and De Causmaecker [23] introduced a generator and dataset of hard 0–1 knapsack instances.

c) Differentiable and parallelization methods: Our training objective is related to work on differentiating through discrete or nonsmooth decision rules. A standard workaround is the straight-through estimator [54], [55]. Yin et al. [33] showed that poor choices of straight-through estimators can induce surrogate-gradient dynamics that are unstable near good minima. Several smoother alternatives have been proposed. Blondel et al. [35] introduced differentiable sorting and ranking operators via isotonic optimization; Berthet et al. [36] smoothed combinatorial optimizers by random perturbation; Amos and Kolter [56] differentiated through the Karush–Kuhn–Tucker conditions of a quadratic program; SparseMAP [37], differentiable dynamic programming [57], and optimal-transport ranking [58] provided further structured alternatives. Our structural gradient is closer in spirit to these surrogates than to a standard straight-through estimator, but is specialized to rank-greedy knapsack selection.

d) Set encoders, controlled dynamics, and alternative sequence models: The encoder we deploy is a permutation-equivariant set encoder: the Set Transformer and its Induced Set-Attention Block (ISAB) [6] provide exact equivariance over the exchangeable item set at $\mathcal{O}(nM_{\text{ind}})$ cost for M_{ind} inducing points. Our training and inference view, in which we predict the initial conditions of a fixed integrator so that its trajectory reaches a target, follows the controlled-dynamics and amortized-inference lineage of neural control of dynamical systems [38]. We additionally evaluated a classic sequence-model alternative: a bidirectional mLSTM [59] reformulated for $\mathcal{O}(\log n)$ parallel depth via the all-prefix-sums (scan) primitive of Blelloch [60], in the spirit of S5-style state-space models [61] and linear recurrent neural networks [62]. Ordering the items forfeits permutation equivariance and did not improve over the set encoder; we report it as a documented negative result in Appendix H.

III. PRELIMINARIES

Throughout the manuscript, we use bold lowercase letters for vectors, bold uppercase letters for matrices, and calligraphic letters for sets and problem classes. A complete notation table is provided in Appendix A.

a) The 0–1 knapsack problem: An instance is a triple $\mathcal{I} = (\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}, C)$ with item values $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$, item weights $\mathbf{w} \in$

$\mathbb{R}_{> 0}^n$, and capacity $C > 0$. The objective is to select a binary indicator $\mathbf{x} \in \{0, 1\}^n$ that solves

$$\max \mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{x} \quad \text{subject to} \quad \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{x} \leq C. \quad (1)$$

We write $z^{\text{IP}}(\mathcal{I})$ for the integer-program optimum and $z^{\text{LP}}(\mathcal{I})$ for the LP relaxation of (1) obtained by relaxing $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$ to $x_i \in [0, 1]$. The associated decision version of the knapsack problem is one of Karp’s twenty-one NP-complete problems [3]. The optimization problem is NP-hard, but admits a fully polynomial-time approximation scheme [24] and has motivated extensive work on exact algorithms and solvers [21], [29], [63].

b) Dantzig’s rule: Dantzig’s rule [34] sorts items by efficiency v_j/w_j in descending order. This order induces the optimal extreme-point solution of the LP relaxation. All items before the *split item* j^* are selected fully, j^* is selected fractionally, and all later items are rejected. We call the integer solution obtained by dropping the fractional split item the LP round-down solution. We denote the corresponding split ratio by

$$\lambda_{\text{raw}} := v_{j^*}/w_{j^*}. \quad (2)$$

If all items fit, there is no split item and we set $\lambda_{\text{raw}} = 0$. The method runs in $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ time, dominated by the initial sort. The subsequent linear scan is $\mathcal{O}(n)$. This $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ sorting cost is the baseline inference scale targeted by the learned ranking component, while the final refinement cost depends on the size of the disagreement core.

c) The Rinnooy Kan family: The multidimensional, or multi-knapsack, problem has m capacity constraints. The constraint matrix is $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ with entries $a_{ij} \geq 0$, and the right-hand side is $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}_{> 0}^m$. The classical generalized-greedy family of Rinnooy Kan, Stougie, and Vercellis [30] is indexed by a nonzero weight vector $\boldsymbol{\lambda} \in \mathbb{R}_{> 0}^m$ on the constraints, with per-item score

$$\sigma_j^{\text{RK}}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) := v_j / \sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i a_{ij}. \quad (3)$$

The algorithm sorts items by $\sigma_j^{\text{RK}}(\boldsymbol{\lambda})$ in descending order and takes items in this order if they fit in every remaining capacity. The case $m = 1$ and $a_{1j} = w_j$ recovers Dantzig’s ratio ordering.

Theorem 1 (Rinnooy Kan, Stougie, and Vercellis [30], Lemma 5.1 and Theorem 5.4). *For a given number of constraints m , assume the following probabilistic model. Items are i.i.d. and their values v_j are nonnegative random variables with a common continuous distribution function that is strictly increasing on a compact support, has bounded density, and has finite mean. Their resource vectors $\mathbf{a}_j \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^m$ are i.i.d. random vectors with positive density on a convex open set and finite first and second moments. The capacities scale linearly with n , namely $b_i = n\beta_i$ with $\beta_i \in (0, \mathbb{E}[a_{i1}])$. Then there exists a unique vector $\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*(\mathcal{D}) \in \mathbb{R}_{> 0}^m \setminus \{\mathbf{0}\}$, determined by the underlying distribution \mathcal{D} and not by the realized instance, such that the simplified generalized-greedy heuristic based on (3) with weights $\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*(\mathcal{D})$ has value z_n^H satisfying*

$$\frac{z_n^H(\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*(\mathcal{D}))}{z_n^{\text{IP}}} \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{} 1 \quad \text{a.s.}$$

The theorem highlights three points relevant to this work. First, the result holds for the multi-knapsack problem with a fixed number of constraints under the specific i.i.d. scaling above. Second, the limiting weight vector $\lambda^*(\mathcal{D})$ that yields asymptotic optimality depends on the distribution but not on the realized instance. This distribution-level structure is what makes it plausible for a single pretrained encoder to learn a stable ranking rule across instances drawn from the same distribution. Third, for the single-knapsack case, $m = 1$ and $a_{1j} = w_j$, the family (3) reduces to Dantzig’s ratio ordering up to multiplication by a positive constant. Thus, varying λ changes only the scale of the scores and not the resulting ordering, which motivates the second generalization of Dantzig’s greedy heuristic introduced below.

d) Extension beyond linear multiplier-ratio scores:

The Rinooy Kan family covers scoring rules of the form $v_j/\langle \lambda, \mathbf{a}_j \rangle$, but a learned scoring rule need not be restricted to this form. The following LP-transfer criterion describes how asymptotic optimality is transferred from the LP relaxation to the greedy solution.

Lemma 2 (LP-transfer criterion). *Consider a sequence of maximization instances with positive integer optimum z_n^{IP} , LP relaxation value z_n^{LP} , and feasible greedy value z_n^{G} . Suppose that*

$$\frac{z_n^{\text{LP}} - z_n^{\text{IP}}}{z_n^{\text{IP}}} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{z_n^{\text{LP}} - z_n^{\text{G}}}{z_n^{\text{LP}}} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{a.s.}$$

Then $z_n^{\text{G}}/z_n^{\text{IP}} \rightarrow 1$ a.s.

Proof. Since z_n^{G} is feasible, $z_n^{\text{G}} \leq z_n^{\text{IP}} \leq z_n^{\text{LP}}$. The first assumption gives $z_n^{\text{LP}}/z_n^{\text{IP}} \rightarrow 1$. Therefore,

$$0 \leq \frac{z_n^{\text{IP}} - z_n^{\text{G}}}{z_n^{\text{IP}}} \leq \frac{z_n^{\text{LP}} - z_n^{\text{G}}}{z_n^{\text{IP}}} = \frac{z_n^{\text{LP}} - z_n^{\text{G}}}{z_n^{\text{LP}}} \frac{z_n^{\text{LP}}}{z_n^{\text{IP}}} \rightarrow 0$$

almost surely. \square

Theorem 1 shows how such a transfer can be verified analytically for the score family $v_j/\langle \lambda, \mathbf{a}_j \rangle$ under a specific i.i.d. scaling model. The architectural point is that a learned score need not itself be of this form. If a learned scoring rule has vanishing relative gap to the LP relaxation on a typical-case distribution, and the LP–IP gap is negligible on that distribution, then the resulting greedy solution is asymptotically optimal.

e) The (p, k) family: For positive item values and weights and real $(p, k) \in \mathbb{R}^2$, we define

$$\sigma_j^{(p,k)} := v_j^p/w_j^k, \quad (4)$$

where $\log \sigma_j^{(p,k)} = p \log v_j - k \log w_j$.

Sorting by $\sigma_j^{(p,k)}$ in descending order and taking items while feasible defines the (p, k) -greedy heuristic. The case $(p, k) = (1, 1)$ is Dantzig’s rule. More generally, when $p = k > 0$, the ordering is the same as Dantzig’s, since $\sigma_j^{(p,p)} = (v_j/w_j)^p$. Choices with $p \neq k$ change the orientation of the level sets in $(\log v, \log w)$ space and can produce rankings that are not determined solely by v_j/w_j .

The empirical advantage of the (p, k) -greedy heuristic over Dantzig’s greedy heuristic is small but consistent. On nine Pisinger benchmark classes with ten instances each at $n = 20$

TABLE I: Per-instance best member of the (p, k) -greedy heuristic compared with Dantzig’s greedy heuristic, evaluated on ten instances from each of nine Pisinger benchmark classes at each size. Since Dantzig’s heuristic corresponds to $(p, k) = (1, 1)$ and this point is included in the swept grid, the per-instance grid argmax can only match or improve on Dantzig. The sweep uses $(p, k) \in [-1, 5]^2$ on a 13×13 grid.

size	strictly better than Dantzig	tied with Dantzig
$n = 20$	76%	24%
$n = 500$	58%	42%

and $n = 500$, the per-instance best member of the swept (p, k) grid strictly improves on Dantzig on a majority of instances and, because Dantzig corresponds to $(p, k) = (1, 1)$ and is included in the grid, never underperforms it (Table I). The best (p^*, k^*) varies substantially within and across benchmark classes, which motivates developing an encoder that predicts an instance-dependent score rather than using a single fixed member of the family.

For each distributional class, one fixed member of the swept (p, k) grid is best on average. A single global choice of (p, k) cannot outperform these class-specific choices when the comparison is restricted to the same grid. An encoder can therefore be used to move beyond a single global rule. It produces scores that can vary from instance to instance. The additional LP-based features introduced in Section VII-C and Section VII-B give the encoder information beyond the two parameters (p, k) , which allows the deployed pipeline of Section IX to improve over fixed (p, k) -greedy heuristics.

f) The oriented circle as a feature: Rather than commit to a single exponent pair, we expose the whole (p, k) family to the encoder as features. Reparameterize (p, k) on the unit circle by a tilt $\theta \in S^1$ with $p = \cos \theta$, $k = \sin \theta$ (the full circle, with no \pm quotient, so antipodal tilts encode opposite orderings). Working in z -scored log-coordinates $\tilde{z}_{v,i}, \tilde{z}_{w,i}$ (Section IX-A), the induced oriented score is

$$\sigma_i^{(\theta)} = \cos \theta \tilde{z}_{v,i} - \sin \theta \tilde{z}_{w,i}, \quad (5)$$

which recovers the Dantzig ratio at $\theta = \frac{\pi}{4}$, value-only ranking at $\theta = 0$, weight-only ranking at $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$, and the anti-Dantzig direction at $\theta = -\frac{3\pi}{4}$. We sample a fixed grid of $J = 8$ tilt angles spanning these regimes and pass the resulting per-item LP coordinates as input channels; the encoder then learns an instance-dependent combination rather than a single global (p, k) . Two further LP-derived biases are mandatory at scale: the sign compass $\beta_i^{\text{sign}} = \text{sign } \Phi_1(i)$ and the empirical-CDF coordinate β^{cdf} of the reduced-cost margin, which prevent the collapse of soft-greedy surrogates at $n \gtrsim 10^4$.

g) Expected polynomial-time bounds on random and smoothed instances: Beier and Vöcking [31] prove that, for broad classes of random and randomly perturbed knapsack instances, the expected number of Pareto-optimal knapsack fillings is polynomially bounded, and the Nemhauser–Ullmann algorithm can enumerate solutions in expected polynomial time. A follow-up analysis of knapsack core algorithms in the tradition of expanding-core methods [63], building on the earlier

core analysis of Goldberg and Marchetti-Spaccamela [64], shows that for uniformly random values and weights the algorithmic core has $\mathcal{O}(\log^3 n)$ items with high probability, and that the resulting exact core algorithm runs in expected time $\mathcal{O}(n \text{ polylog}(n))$ [32]. Based on these results, we use the term core for the set of items whose inclusion in the optimal solution is not yet determined after solving the LP relaxation. In our framework, improving the lower bound shrinks this undecided set monotonically (Lemma 5), so stronger lower bounds leave a smaller exact search problem. The empirical core sizes observed on our benchmarks are reported in Section XI.

IV. WORST-CASE LIMITS AND APPROXIMATE MODELS

a) Polynomial-inference setting: Let \mathcal{C} be an NP-hard combinatorial optimization problem class and let n denote the input size. We consider a finite-precision neural inference procedure consisting of a polynomial-time-computable feature map $\phi_n: \mathcal{C}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d(n)}$, where $d(n) = \text{poly}(n)$ and \mathcal{C}_n denotes the instances of size n , together with a neural state-transition map $F_{\theta_n}: \mathbb{R}^{d(n)} \times \mathcal{S}_n \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_n$. The map F_{θ_n} maps the current feature representation and internal state to an updated state and is evaluable in polynomial time. The procedure performs at most $\text{poly}(n)$ forward iterations and then decodes a feasible solution in polynomial time.

We next formalize the classical NP-hardness barrier in neural-architecture terms.

Proposition 3 (Worst-case barrier). *Suppose that, for every instance $\mathcal{I} \in \mathcal{C}$, the procedure*

$$s_{t+1} = F_{\theta_n}(\phi_n(\mathcal{I}), s_t)$$

terminates after at most $\text{poly}(n)$ iterations and returns an optimal feasible solution. Then $P = NP$.

Proof. The feature map, each forward iteration, and the final decoding step run in polynomial time by assumption. Since the number of iterations is polynomial, the full inference procedure is a polynomial-time algorithm for the optimization problem. The associated decision problem can therefore also be solved in polynomial time, which implies $P = NP$. \square

The polynomial-inference assumption covers the standard neural architectures considered in this paper, including feed-forward, recurrent, attentional, autoregressive, and prompt-conditioned models, provided that their per-instance inference cost is polynomial in n . An architecture falls outside the scope of Proposition 3 only by violating this assumption, for example by running an internal branch-and-bound or exhaustive-search procedure whose worst-case runtime is super-polynomial in n . Such a procedure may still be an effective exact solver, but it no longer qualifies as a bounded-inference foundational model in the sense used in this paper.

b) Hard-instance benchmarks: Proposition 3 is a worst-case statement. Under the standard assumption $P \neq NP$, it implies that a bounded-inference model cannot solve every instance exactly, but it does not identify the failing instances. Instance-space analysis, as used by Smith–Miles, Christiansen, and Muñoz [22], and the explicit hard-instance generator of Jookan, Leyman, and De Causmaecker [23] provide practical

ways to probe this limitation. A useful foundational-model claim for knapsack should therefore be framed not as exact worst-case solvability, but as approximate performance on specified instance distributions.

c) Typical-case asymptotics and model structure: The exact barrier does not rule out a useful approximate model. Theorem 1 shows that, under its i.i.d. scaling assumptions, a generalized-greedy weight vector determined by the distribution yields asymptotic optimality. Beier and Vöcking’s analyses of random knapsack and knapsack core algorithms [31], [32] provide complementary evidence that exact knapsack methods can be efficient in expectation under random input models, and that refinement around the fractional solution can avoid exhaustive search. These results suggest a useful regime in which three quantities remain controlled: (i) the relative LP–IP gap, (ii) the greedy gap to the LP relaxation, and (iii) the size of the residual core passed to exact refinement. We use these observations as structural motivation, not as a worst-case guarantee for all benchmark distributions. Quantity (i) is also the source of the off-relaxation ceiling discussed in the introduction: a fixed continuous landscape equal to the LP relaxation attracts to the LP vertex \bar{x} , leaving the integer optimum \mathbf{x}^* off-manifold by the integrality gap. The flow-based encoder of Section IX relocates this ceiling to the boundary of the training distribution, and the residual core of (iii) is exactly the set on which the deploy-time decoder of Section IX-H operates.

Our pipeline follows this structure. A learned encoder produces instance-dependent scores, and a reduced-cost peel restricts the rounding to a small residual core. The refinement inside that core is modular. We use a risk-seeking Monte-Carlo decode by default, and any solver, including an exact dynamic program on the items where the leading candidates disagree, can be used in its place. The cost of this final step depends on the size of the residual core, which is measured empirically in Section XI rather than treated as part of the bounded neural forward pass.

For the single-knapsack problem, varying the Rinnooy Kan weight changes only the scale of the scores and does not generate orderings beyond Dantzig’s rule. The (p, k) family (4) provides a richer collection of fixed rules, but no single member should be expected to dominate across all instances (Proposition 6). This is why the encoder is used to produce scores that adapt from instance to instance, and why a mixture of scoring heads is natural.

V. CHALLENGES AND PIPELINE OVERVIEW

Three obstacles have historically limited learned solvers for the 0–1 knapsack problem and related mixed-integer programs. We list them with our remedy, which the rest of the paper develops in detail.

a) Sample efficiency: A common approach in neural combinatorial optimization uses policy gradients with hard-decision constructive heads [8], [11]. In knapsack-specific work, sequence-to-sequence models with attention have also been trained from solver-generated examples [19]. In both cases, the learning signal is indirect. It is either a realized return or

a target decision sequence, rather than a differentiable signal derived from the LP geometry and the capacity constraint. We avoid reinforcement-learning rollouts altogether and instead train against the rank-violation gap to an LP-induced reference ranking (§VIII). No policy-gradient estimator is needed.

b) Inference cost: Self-attention has $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ pairwise interactions per layer-head, which at $n = 20,000$ amounts to 4×10^8 terms per layer per head. Dense graph-neural-network message passing has the same quadratic dependence on the number of items. The Dantzig baseline runs in $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ time. The encoder we deploy is designed to achieve the same asymptotic inference cost, and we describe it next. We also studied a parallel-scan reformulation of the bidirectional mLSTM cell of Beck et al. [59], built on the affine-recurrence prefix-sum primitive of Blelloch [60], which runs in $\mathcal{O}(\log n)$ parallel depth, but it forfeits permutation equivariance and did not improve over the set encoder; we report it in Appendix H. The encoder we deploy is the permutation-equivariant set encoder of Section IX, an ISAB trunk with $\mathcal{O}(nM_{\text{ind}}d)$ cost for M_{ind} inducing points, followed by a *fixed* number k_{leap} of damped symplectic leapfrog steps, each $\mathcal{O}(n)$ via a Sherman–Morrison metric inverse; the rollout cost is therefore $\mathcal{O}(k_{\text{leap}} n)$ and independent of the instance. The default refinement is a Monte-Carlo/CVaR decode that draws M Bernoulli roundings and repairs each in $\mathcal{O}(n)$, for $\mathcal{O}(Mn)$ total. An exact dynamic program on the reduced-cost core of size K_{core} with residual capacity c_{core} , costing $\mathcal{O}(K_{\text{core}} c_{\text{core}})$ in the array formulation (less with a nondominated-state list), is an alternative refinement. The residual-core size is measured empirically in Section XI.

c) Differentiable selection: A common workaround is the straight-through estimator [54], [55], which uses the discrete decision in the forward pass and a surrogate derivative in the backward pass. Related straight-through approaches have also been used in recent neural-network methods for inventory-control problems [38]. Yin et al. [33] show that the behavior of straight-through estimators depends critically on the chosen surrogate. Suitable coarse gradients can align with the population gradient, whereas poor choices can be unstable near local minima. For capacity-respecting greedy selection, an identity backward map does not encode how far an item is from being correctly ranked relative to the capacity cutoff.

A smoother alternative is to train a sigmoid head with binary cross-entropy on greedy-take labels. This avoids the discontinuity, but its gradient is controlled by classification confidence rather than by the rank violation that determines the greedy solution. In our experiments (§XI, Appendix E), this mismatch leads to overfitting at small training sizes and unstable out-of-distribution scores at high encoder capacity. Existing differentiable-ranking and structured surrogate methods, including soft-rank [35], perturbed combinatorial optimizers [36], optimal-transport ranking [58], SparseMAP [37], and differentiable dynamic programming [57], provide general tools for smoothing discrete decisions, but they are not tailored to capacity-respecting greedy knapsack selection. We therefore use a closed-form structural gradient (§VIII) whose magnitude is the per-item rank-violation gap to the LP-induced ranking and whose direction moves the item across the greedy

capacity cutoff. The LP-induced ranking is a zero-gradient region of the resulting gradient flow.

d) Two backward signals: structural gradient versus REINFORCE: The structural gradient above is a straight-through estimator: it keeps the discrete greedy decode in the forward pass and supplies a closed-form, *biased but low-variance* surrogate in the backward pass, whose direction is the rank violation. It is decode-agnostic and trains the encoder cheaply, but its bias means it cannot by itself optimize a sampling-based decoder. The deploy-time decoder is instead a Monte-Carlo rounding of the relaxed state, for which the score-function (REINFORCE) estimator is *unbiased but high-variance*, with variance growing with the number of sampled coordinates. We combine the two: a self-critical baseline (the encoder-greedy value) cancels the leading variance of the REINFORCE term while preserving its unbiasedness, and the structural gradient supplies a stable low-variance backbone. Concretely, training mixes the structural loss with a tail-REINFORCE term restricted to the reduced-cost core (Section IX and Appendix G), so the unbiased signal is concentrated on the few LP-uncertain items where it matters.

VI. LP TRANSFORMATION AND REDUCED-COST BANDS

We now develop the geometry that the encoder operates on. This geometry defines both the feature map and the rank-based loss.

a) LP transformation: Let λ_{raw} be the split ratio induced by the Dantzig rule, as defined in Eq. (2). Define the reduced profit

$$\bar{c}_j := v_j - \lambda_{\text{raw}} w_j \quad (6)$$

and the two per-item transformation coordinates

$$\Phi_1(j) := \frac{\bar{c}_j}{V_{\text{tot}}}, \quad \Phi_2(j) := \log(w_j/C), \quad (7)$$

where $V_{\text{tot}} = \sum_j v_j$. The coordinate Φ_1 is the normalized signed reduced profit relative to the LP split ratio: $\Phi_1(j) > 0$ places item j on the selected side of the LP threshold, $\Phi_1(j) < 0$ on the rejected side, and $\Phi_1(j) = 0$ corresponds to a tie with the split ratio. The coordinate Φ_2 provides a secondary log-weight scale.

b) LP round-down partition and reduced-cost band: Let \hat{x} denote the LP round-down solution induced by Dantzig’s ratio order and let x^{IP} be an optimal integer solution. The two binary attributes \hat{x}_j and x_j^{IP} partition the item set into four classes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_+ &= \{j: \hat{x}_j = 1, x_j^{\text{IP}} = 1\} && \text{(present in both),} \\ \mathcal{V} &= \{j: \hat{x}_j = 0, x_j^{\text{IP}} = 1\} && \text{(present in optimal),} \\ \mathcal{R} &= \{j: \hat{x}_j = 1, x_j^{\text{IP}} = 0\} && \text{(absent in optimal),} \\ \mathcal{K}_- &= \{j: \hat{x}_j = 0, x_j^{\text{IP}} = 0\} && \text{(absent in both).} \end{aligned}$$

The ideal residual set is $\mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{R}$. These are the items on which the LP round-down solution and the integer optimum disagree. The first useful fact is that this residual set is confined to a narrow reduced-cost band.

Lemma 4 (Reduced-cost band bound). *Let $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ be the LP round-down solution. Every $j \in \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{R}$ satisfies*

$$|\bar{c}_j| \leq z^{\text{LP}} - z^{\text{IP}}.$$

As a result, we have

$$|\Phi_1(j)| \leq \frac{V_{\max}}{V_{\text{tot}}}, \quad V_{\max} := \max_j v_j.$$

Proof. The all-fit case is trivial, so assume that a split item exists. Since $\bar{c}_j = v_j - \lambda_{\text{raw}} w_j$, the LP value can be written as

$$z^{\text{LP}} = \lambda_{\text{raw}} C + \sum_{\bar{c}_j > 0} \bar{c}_j.$$

For any feasible integer solution \mathbf{x} ,

$$\begin{aligned} z^{\text{LP}} - \mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{x} &= \lambda_{\text{raw}} (C - \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{x}) \\ &\quad + \sum_{\bar{c}_j > 0} (1 - x_j) \bar{c}_j + \sum_{\bar{c}_j < 0} x_j (-\bar{c}_j) \\ &\geq \sum_{\bar{c}_j > 0} (1 - x_j) \bar{c}_j + \sum_{\bar{c}_j < 0} x_j (-\bar{c}_j). \end{aligned}$$

The LP round-down solution $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ takes all items with $\bar{c}_j > 0$ and rejects all items with $\bar{c}_j < 0$, up to zero-reduced-cost ties. Therefore, when the inequality is applied to \mathbf{x}^{IP} , every item on which $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and \mathbf{x}^{IP} disagree contributes $|\bar{c}_j|$ to the right-hand side. Hence

$$|\bar{c}_j| \leq z^{\text{LP}} - z^{\text{IP}} \quad \text{for all } j \in \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{R}.$$

Finally, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is feasible and the fractional LP solution differs from it by at most a fraction of the split item, so

$$z^{\text{LP}} - z^{\text{IP}} \leq z^{\text{LP}} - \mathbf{v}^\top \hat{\mathbf{x}} \leq v_{j^*} \leq V_{\max}.$$

Dividing by V_{tot} gives the stated bound on $|\Phi_1(j)|$. \square

This reduced-cost band is the analogue of the classical knapsack core. The core analysis of Beier and Vöcking [32] motivates restricting exact refinement to a small residual set.

c) Core monotonicity under improved lower bounds:

Better lower bounds shrink the reduced-cost core. We first state this monotonicity property independently of how the lower bound is obtained.

Lemma 5 (Core monotonicity in the lower bound). *Let $z^A \leq z^B$ be two feasible lower bounds on the integer optimum. For a lower bound z , define the reduced-cost core*

$$\text{core}(z) := \{j: |\bar{c}_j| \leq z^{\text{LP}} - z\},$$

where \bar{c}_j is the reduced profit as defined in Eq. (6). Then

$$\text{core}(z^B) \subseteq \text{core}(z^A).$$

Proof. Since $z^A \leq z^B$, we have

$$z^{\text{LP}} - z^A \geq z^{\text{LP}} - z^B.$$

The reduced profits \bar{c}_j do not depend on the lower bound, so the inclusion follows immediately from the definition of $\text{core}(z)$. \square

Proposition 6 (No uniform fixed- (p, k) dominance). *For every fixed $(p^*, k^*) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ with $p^* \neq k^*$, there exists a 0–1 knapsack instance on which*

$$z^{(p^*, k^*)} < z^{(1, 1)}.$$

A counterexample construction is given in Appendix B. Together with the empirical results presented in Table I, this suggests that no fixed choice of (p, k) consistently dominates across all instances. Any empirical advantage of such a rule is therefore distributional or instance-dependent rather than worst-case. This motivates using an encoder that produces instance-dependent scores, while retaining Dantzig as a candidate solution in the final pool.

d) Band hierarchy and core reduction: Let

$$B_{\text{IP-LP}} := \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{R}, \quad B_{\text{core}}(z) := \{j: |\bar{c}_j| \leq z^{\text{LP}} - z\},$$

and

$$B_{\text{LP}} := \left\{ j: |\Phi_1(j)| \leq \frac{V_{\max}}{V_{\text{tot}}} \right\}.$$

Let z_{best} denote the best value obtained from the swept (p, k) family. Since $(1, 1)$ is included in this family,

$$\underbrace{B_{\text{IP-LP}}}_{\text{ideal residual set}} \subseteq \underbrace{B_{\text{core}}(z^{\text{best-}\mathcal{F}})}_{\text{best } (p, k) \text{ core}} \subseteq \underbrace{B_{\text{core}}(z^{(1, 1)})}_{(1, 1) \text{ core}} \subseteq \underbrace{B_{\text{LP}}}_{\text{Lemma 4}}. \quad (8)$$

The first inclusion follows from Lemma 4, and the second from Corollary 10 (stated in Appendix B). The last inclusion follows because $z^{(1, 1)}$ is at least the LP round-down value. Better lower bounds shrink the reduced-cost core, so a learned encoder that selects a good (p, k) rule, or more generally a good score $\sigma^{(p, k)}$, reduces the residual set before exact refinement. This reduced-cost core is precisely the peel set on which the deploy-time decoder of Section IX-H operates: the encoder lowers the bound, shrinking the core, and the Monte-Carlo/CVaR decoder then refines only the remaining undecided items.

On an almost-strongly-correlated instance from the Pisinger benchmark set with $n = 80$, the observed set sizes are

$$|B_{\text{LP}}| = 80, \quad |B_{\text{core}}(z^{(1, 1)})| = 54, \quad |B_{\text{IP-LP}}| = 2.$$

The set $B_{\text{IP-LP}}$ is the ideal residual set but is not known at inference time. The deploy-time decoder therefore operates on a computable residual set, the reduced-cost core, rather than on this ideal set. Worked examples and additional plots are provided in Appendix D.

VII. FEATURE ALIASING AND THE LIFT

The projection (Φ_1, Φ_2) does not uniquely determine the correct decision for an item. Different items or decision states can share the same projected coordinates while belonging to different optimal solutions. We refer to this phenomenon as *feature aliasing*. The lift introduced below augments the LP coordinates with additional state and tie-breaking information that separates the most important aliasing cases in the 0–1 knapsack setting.

Fig. 1: Pattern-recognition AUC for LP-IP-band membership across feature representations. The bars report ROC-AUC under instance-grouped 5-fold cross-validation (mean \pm std) for logistic regression and a 32-hidden-unit MLP, with the dashed line marking the chance level of 0.5. F0: raw (v, w) features; F1: LP projection (Φ_1, Φ_2) ; F2: coordinate dispersion; F3: arcsinh compression; F4: F2 plus residual-capacity lift; F5: full lift; F6: full lift plus LP-derived global features. The MLP AUC rises from 0.71 at F1 to 0.89 at F6, which indicates that the lifted representation adds discriminative information beyond the two LP coordinates. Detailed results are reported in Appendix C.

A. Three types of aliasing

Definition 7 (Feature aliasing). A feature map $\phi: \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ exhibits *feature aliasing* if there exist states $s_1, s_2 \in \mathcal{S}$ with $\phi(s_1) = \phi(s_2)$ but $T(s_1) \neq T(s_2)$, where $T(s)$ denotes the target decision at state s .

a) *Type A, context aliasing near the LP frontier*: Items with Φ_1 close to zero lie near the LP split threshold. Their integer decision can depend on the residual capacity and on which other items have already been selected. Static per-item LP coordinates do not encode this decision context.

b) *Type B, tie aliasing*: If two items in the same instance have identical (Φ_1, Φ_2) coordinates. Such items are interchangeable for the knapsack objective, but a deterministic training label may still select one representative and not the other. A stable tie-breaking coordinate makes this convention visible to the model.

c) *Type C, multiplicity aliasing*: In bounded knapsack variants, the same item type can appear with multiple available copies. Static per-item coordinates do not encode how many copies have already been selected. This case is not active in the 0-1 setting studied here, but the same lift idea can be extended by adding copy-count or residual-stock coordinates.

B. The lift

The LP coordinates (Φ_1, Φ_2) describe an item relative to the LP split threshold, but they do not encode the current decision state. In particular, two items with identical projected

coordinates may still require different decisions if the remaining knapsack capacity differs. This is the feature-aliasing issue introduced above.

To distinguish such cases, we augment the feature vector with the normalized residual capacity C_t/C , where C_t is the remaining capacity when item j is evaluated. We also include a stable-rank coordinate r_j that provides deterministic tie-breaking for coincident items during supervised training. The lifted representation is

$$\phi(j; \mathcal{I}) = (\Phi_1(j), \Phi_2(j), C_t/C, r_j, \text{global features}). \quad (9)$$

C. Coordinate dispersion

The projected coordinates can be highly concentrated near the LP frontier. We therefore apply an instance-wise empirical-CDF transform to each coordinate to obtain

$$\tilde{\Phi}_k(j) := G_k(\Phi_k(j); \mathcal{I}), \quad k \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (10)$$

where $G_k(\cdot; \mathcal{I})$ is the empirical CDF of Φ_k over the items in the current instance. This rank transform maps each coordinate to $[0, 1]$ and approximately uniformizes the marginal empirical distributions, while preserving the within-coordinate order. Other coordinate-dispersion transforms may also be used.

Proposition 8 (Order preservation under coordinate dispersion). *For any two items i, j , the empirical-CDF transform (10) satisfies*

$$\Phi_1(i) < \Phi_1(j) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \tilde{\Phi}_1(i) \leq \tilde{\Phi}_1(j).$$

With deterministic tie-breaking in the ranks, the transformed coordinate preserves the full item order.

The claim follows immediately from monotonicity of the empirical-CDF transform.

D. The lift adds information: empirical validation

We use a simple pattern-recognition experiment to test whether the feature transformations introduced in this section add useful information. The task is to predict, for each item, membership in the LP–IP disagreement band from per-item features. The data consist of 300 hard instances from the Pisinger benchmark set with $n = 40$ across eight benchmark classes. We train a 32-hidden-unit MLP and report ROC-AUC under 5-fold cross-validation. Full experimental details are given in Appendix C, and the main results are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 supports four conclusions. First, the LP projection is more informative than raw (v, w) features for this diagnostic task. Second, coordinate dispersion preserves the relevant one-dimensional order but does not by itself improve AUC. Third, arcsinh compression performs similarly to the LP-projection baseline. Fourth, the lifted features improve AUC over the LP baseline (+7% AUC over LP baseline, statistically significant under 5-fold CV), suggesting that residual-capacity and tie-breaking information help resolve the feature-aliasing cases identified above. We use folds grouped by instance to avoid placing items from the same knapsack instance in both train and test splits.

VIII. A STRUCTURAL GRADIENT OPERATOR FOR GREEDY SELECTION

This structural operator is the strongest single supervision signal in our pipeline. We present two instances of it. The swap-hinge below is the headline operator; the separable-quadratic L-move loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{move}}^{\text{OPT}}$ of Eq. (32), introduced with the flow encoder in Section IX, is a generalization that supervises only the Dantzig-versus-optimum symmetric difference. Both keep a discrete forward decode and attach a closed-form backward signal. They are straight-through estimators in spirit, and both depend only on the should-add/should-drop masks, so they apply to any binary mixed-integer program with inequality constraints, not only to knapsack. Greedy selection is discontinuous as a function of the score vector σ . Away from rank boundaries, small score perturbations do not change the selected set, while the selection can change abruptly when ranks cross near the capacity cutoff. We therefore keep the greedy forward pass and attach to it a structural backward operator whose signal is tied to rank violations.

A. Identity straight-through estimators are insufficient

Identity straight-through estimators and closely related surrogate-gradient methods replace the derivative of a discrete decision by an identity backward map [54], [55]. Yin et al. [33] show that the usefulness of such a surrogate depends critically on the backward signal. Well-chosen coarse gradients can align with the population gradient, whereas poor choices can be unstable near local minima. For capacity-respecting greedy

selection, the identity surrogate is too coarse. It does not encode how far an item is from crossing the capacity cutoff or from correcting a rank inversion. Near the cutoff, different rank violations can therefore receive essentially the same backward signal, which we observe to produce oscillations between nearby swap configurations.

B. Binary cross-entropy is insufficient for rank-greedy training

A smooth alternative to a straight-through estimator is to train a sigmoid head with binary cross-entropy (BCE) on target take labels. Binary cross-entropy avoids the discontinuity, but it optimizes classification confidence rather than the rank relation that determines the greedy solution. Once an item is correctly ordered, an optimizer may still try to minimize the BCE loss, even though the greedy solution depends only on relative order. In our experiments, this mismatch leads to overfitting at small training sizes and unstable out-of-distribution scores at $n = 20,000$ with high-capacity encoders (Appendix E).

C. Rank-violation gradient

A natural alternative is to regress scores toward fixed target values, for example $+1$ for selected items and -1 for rejected items. This also gives the wrong training signal. Once an item is correctly ordered, an optimizer may still try to minimize the regression loss, even though the greedy solution depends only on relative order. The gradient magnitude is therefore tied to distance from the chosen target value rather than to the item’s rank violation.

As in Section VI, let \mathcal{V} denote target-selected items missed by greedy, and let \mathcal{R} denote greedily selected items rejected by the target.

Let

$$\tau_+ := \min_{i \in \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{K}_+} \sigma_i, \quad \tau_- := \max_{i \in \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{K}_-} \sigma_i,$$

be, respectively, the weakest target-selected score and the strongest target-rejected score. We use stop-gradient on τ_+ and τ_- . The swap-hinge loss is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{swap}}(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} (\tau_- + \mu - \sigma_i)_+^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{R}} (\sigma_i - \tau_+ + \mu)_+^2, \quad (11)$$

where $\mu > 0$ is a margin and $(x)_+ := \max(x, 0)$ denotes the positive-part operator. The first term raises missed target items above the strongest target-rejected score by margin μ ; the second lowers wrongly selected items below the weakest target-selected score by the same margin. If the greedy selection matches the target, then $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{R} = \emptyset$ and the swap term vanishes.

With the cutoffs τ_+ and τ_- treated as constants, we define

$$g_i^{\text{swap}} := \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_{\text{swap}}}{\partial \sigma_i} = \begin{cases} -(\tau_- + \mu - \sigma_i)_+, & i \in \mathcal{V}, \\ (\sigma_i - \tau_+ + \mu)_+, & i \in \mathcal{R}, \\ 0. & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Gradient descent therefore raises missed target items and lowers wrongly selected items.

D. Dense supervision by soft bands

The deployed flow encoder (Section IX) adds a margin term to the band that points at the *oracle* band rather than the nearest band. Penalizing the squared distance to the target band, dist^2 , yields a gradient $\partial_q \text{dist}^2 \propto \text{dist}$ that grows with the distance from the target, so items far on the wrong side are corrected more strongly. This is in contrast to the target-agnostic closest-band penalty, whose gradient can oppose the swap and band terms; the swap-band-margin loss is stated as $\mathcal{L}_{\text{SWBM}}$ in Eq. (30). The swap term supervises only the disagreement sets \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{R} . Items in the agreement classes \mathcal{K}_+ and \mathcal{K}_- receive no direct signal. Since all scores are produced by the shared model $\sigma_i = f_\theta(\phi(j_i))$, updates from the disagreement items can also move agreement items. We therefore add a soft per-class band.

Let the acceptable score interval for class $y \in \{0, 1\}$ be $[\sigma_y^{\text{lo}}, \sigma_y^{\text{hi}}]$, with

$$\begin{aligned} [\sigma_1^{\text{lo}}, \sigma_1^{\text{hi}}] &= [1 - W/2, 1 + W/2], \\ [\sigma_0^{\text{lo}}, \sigma_0^{\text{hi}}] &= [-1 - W/2, -1 + W/2]. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

We use $W = 0.5$ in the experiments. The band gradient is

$$g_i^{\text{band}} = -(\sigma_{y_i}^{\text{lo}} - \sigma_i)_+ + (\sigma_i - \sigma_{y_i}^{\text{hi}})_+. \quad (14)$$

It is zero inside the class band, negative below it, and positive above it. Thus, gradient descent moves scores back toward the acceptable interval without forcing them to match a single target value.

The full structural backward signal is

$$g_i = g_i^{\text{swap}} + \beta_{\text{band}} g_i^{\text{band}}, \quad \beta_{\text{band}} = 0.5. \quad (15)$$

This vector is attached to the greedy forward pass as the custom vector-Jacobian product.

E. Zero-gradient region and role of the two gradient terms

The proposed structural gradient does not single out one unique score vector. Instead, it defines a zero-gradient region. If the greedy prediction matches the target and all scores lie inside their class bands, then no update is applied.

Proposition 9 (Local band stability). *Suppose the greedy prediction matches the target and $\sigma_i \in [\sigma_{y_i}^{\text{lo}}, \sigma_{y_i}^{\text{hi}}]$ for all items i . Then $g(\sigma) = 0$. If the greedy prediction remains unchanged but a coordinate leaves its class band, the band gradient moves that coordinate back toward the acceptable interval under gradient descent.*

Proof. If the greedy prediction matches the target, then $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{R} = \emptyset$, so the swap term vanishes. If σ_i lies inside its class band, both positive-part terms in (14) are zero, so $g_i^{\text{band}} = 0$.

If $\sigma_i < \sigma_{y_i}^{\text{lo}}$, then $g_i^{\text{band}} < 0$, and gradient descent increases σ_i . If $\sigma_i > \sigma_{y_i}^{\text{hi}}$, then $g_i^{\text{band}} > 0$, and gradient descent decreases σ_i . Thus the update direction points back toward the class band whenever a coordinate leaves it. \square

The two gradient terms (12) and (14) stabilize different failure modes. The swap term provides the rank-correction signal on $\mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{R}$. Missed target items are pushed upward in score, and wrongly selected items are pushed downward

whenever they violate the swap margin. Because \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{R} are defined after the capacity-respecting greedy pass, this correction is tied to the realized greedy decision. The band term provides dense supervision on all items and prevents drift on scores that are already consistent with the target. Together, the two terms leave target-consistent rankings unchanged while providing corrective gradients when the greedy selection or class-band constraints are violated. In Appendix E, we compare the described structural gradient operator with alternative variants.

IX. HAMILTONIAN PRIMAL-DUAL FLOW ON A FIXED LP LANDSCAPE

The structural operator of Section VIII differentiates a single greedy decode. We now replace that single forward pass with a short *dynamical* one. A permutation-equivariant set encoder predicts the kinetics $(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0)$ of a continuous relaxation, a *fixed* symplectic integrator transports that state across an interior-point energy landscape, and a reduced-cost decoder rounds the terminal point. The dynamics combine Hamiltonian descent on the primal variables [65] with primal-dual saddle ascent on the multiplier [66], integrated by a structure-preserving symplectic scheme [67]. The landscape itself is *not* learned in this section. It is the augmented Lagrangian of the LP relaxation [68] plus a log-barrier, so the only learnable object is the map from an instance to a good place to start the flow. We explore learning the landscape itself, oracle-free, in Appendix G.

Throughout, $\mathbf{q} \in (0, 1)^n$ is the continuous flow state (the relaxed decision variable); the LP optimum $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is one point on its trajectory), $\mathbf{x}^* \in \{0, 1\}^n$ is the integer optimum we supervise on, capacity is C , and the single knapsack constraint has multiplier $\lambda \geq 0$ (so $m = 1$). We write $g(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{q} - C$.

A. Tilted-coordinate feature lift

The encoder consumes the lift $\phi(j; \mathcal{I})$ of Section VII-B, instantiated by sampling the oriented (p, k) circle of Section III at $J = 8$ angles. With per-instance $v, w > 0$ we form z -scored log-coordinates

$$\tilde{z}_{v,i} = \frac{\log v_i - \overline{\log v}}{\text{std}(\log v) + \epsilon}, \quad \tilde{z}_{w,i} = \frac{\log w_i - \overline{\log w}}{\text{std}(\log w) + \epsilon}, \quad (16)$$

with $\epsilon = 10^{-9}$. Each regime fixes a tilt $\theta \in \{0, \frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3\pi}{4}, \pi, -\frac{3\pi}{4}, -\frac{\pi}{2}, -\frac{\pi}{4}\}$ on the full circle S^1 (no \pm quotient), sets $p = \cos \theta$, $k = \sin \theta$, and induces the oriented score

$$\sigma_i^{(\theta)} = \cos \theta \tilde{z}_{v,i} - \sin \theta \tilde{z}_{w,i}, \quad (17)$$

which recovers the Dantzig ratio at $\theta = \frac{\pi}{4}$, value-only at $\theta = 0$, weight-only at $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$, and the anti-Dantzig direction at $\theta = -\frac{3\pi}{4}$. Sorting descending in $\sigma^{(\theta)}$, accumulating $S_r = \sum_{j \leq r} w_{\pi_j}$, and locating the LP break $j^* = \min\{r : S_r > C\}$ with break score σ_{j^*} , the per-regime block is the LP-induced coordinates of Eq. (7) together with their rank-compactified copulas $\hat{\Phi}_k = G_k(\Phi_k; \mathcal{I})$ and the sign compass β^{sign} :

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_1(i) &= \text{clip}(\sigma_i^{(\theta)} - \sigma_{j^*}, -10, 10), \\ \Phi_2(i) &= \text{clip}\left(\frac{S_{\text{rank}(i)}}{C} - 1, -3, 3\right), \\ \hat{\Phi}_1(i) &= \hat{F}(\Phi_1)(i), \quad \hat{\Phi}_2(i) = \hat{F}(\Phi_2)(i), \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Fig. 2: Hamiltonian primal–dual inference pipeline. An instance $(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}, C)$ is mapped to the $F=43$ tilted (p, k) + rank-copula lift ϕ , encoded by the permutation-equivariant ISAB trunk f_θ into the flow kinetics $(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0)$, and transported by $k_{\text{leap}}=16$ damped symplectic leapfrog steps over the *fixed* augmented-Lagrangian landscape V_{LP} plus log-barriers (teal group, §IX). The terminal $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}$ is rounded by the reduced-cost peel to a core of size K_{core} and a risk-seeking CVaR- β Monte-Carlo decode (best-of- M over the upper β -superquantile), returning the integer solution \mathbf{x} . The learned-landscape extension (Appendix G, red) leaves this pipeline unchanged and only adds two oracle-free heads on the same trunk: a residual potential Φ_θ^{res} that carves an \mathbf{x}^* -basin and a Riemannian metric M_θ that reshapes the geodesics.

and $\beta^{\text{sign}}(i) = \text{sign } \Phi_1(i)$, where Φ_1 is the signed reduced-cost margin to the LP break (β^{cdf}), Φ_2 the signed capacity overshoot at the item, and $\widehat{F}(\cdot) \in [0, 1]$ the empirical-CDF rank. Stacking the J regimes (five channels each) and appending three global features $[v, w, \log(v/w)]$ gives

$$F = 5J + 3 = 5 \cdot 8 + 3 = 43 \quad (19)$$

columns, each finally renormalized $\mathbf{f}_{:,j} \leftarrow \mathbf{f}_{:,j} / (|\mathbf{f}_{:,j}| + 10^{-9})$ so the inputs are scale-invariant across n .

B. Permutation-equivariant encoder of the flow kinetics

The encoder f_θ is an Induced Set-Attention Block (ISAB) trunk [6], chosen for exact permutation equivariance over the exchangeable item set. An input projection $H^{(0)} = \text{GELU}(\mathbf{f}W_{\text{in}} + b_{\text{in}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$ feeds L stacked ISAB blocks, each with M_{ind} inducing points $I \in \mathbb{R}^{M_{\text{ind}} \times d}$ and the OOD-safe $1/\sqrt{n}$ attention temperature

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \text{softmax}(n^{-1/2}(IW_{q1})(HW_{k1})^\top), \\ S &= \text{LN}(I + A_1HW_{v1}), \\ A_2 &= \text{softmax}(n^{-1/2}(HW_{q2})(SW_{k2})^\top), \\ H' &= \text{LN}(H + A_2SW_{v2}), \\ H^{(\ell+1)} &= \text{LN}(H' + \text{GELU}(H'W_{f1} + b_{f1})W_{f2} + b_{f2}), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

with feed-forward width $4d$ and $O(nM_{\text{ind}}d)$ cost. The kinetics head reads the final embedding $H \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$ and emits the flow's initial conditions,

$$(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0) = f_\theta(\phi(\mathcal{I})), \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q}_0 &= \text{clip}(\zeta(HW_q + b_q), 10^{-3}, 1 - 10^{-3}), \\ \mathbf{p}_0 &= HW_p + b_p, \\ \lambda_0 &= \text{softplus}\left(\left[\overline{H} \parallel \sqrt{\text{Var } H} + \epsilon\right]W_\lambda + b_\lambda\right), \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $\zeta(\cdot)$ is the logistic sigmoid (written ζ , not σ , to avoid clashing with the score σ), $W_q, W_p \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times 1}$ and $W_\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{2d \times 1}$ pools the item-wise mean and standard deviation. The primal momentum \mathbf{p}_0 is the relational steering lever: it is initialized near zero ($W_p \sim 0.01$), as are the biases $b_q = -1.10$ ($\mathbf{q}_0 \approx 0.25$) and $b_\lambda = -1.0$ ($\lambda_0 \approx 0.31$), giving a sane interior start. Here \mathbf{q}_0 replaces the analytic score σ as the encoder output; σ is retained only for the closed (p, k) score of Section III. The deployed configuration $d=128$, $M_{\text{ind}}=48$, $L=3$ with the $F=43$ lift has 716,931 learnable parameters (≈ 717 k).

C. Fixed augmented-Lagrangian landscape

The flow moves on a *fixed* potential: the linear LP objective drift, the multiplier coupling, a Bertsekas quadratic augmentation of the capacity violation, and log-barriers confining \mathbf{q} to the box and to the capacity half-space,

$$\begin{aligned} V(\mathbf{q}, \lambda) &= -\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{q} + \lambda g(\mathbf{q}) \\ &\quad + \frac{\beta_{\text{aug}}}{2} \max(0, g(\mathbf{q}))^2 \\ &\quad - \rho_{\text{box}} \sum_i (\log q_i + \log(1 - q_i)) \\ &\quad - \rho_{\text{cap}} \log(C - \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{q}). \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

The forces $\nabla_{\mathbf{q}}V$ and $\nabla_{\lambda}V = g(\mathbf{q})$ are obtained by automatic differentiation. Constants are $\beta_{\text{aug}} = 0.5$ and $\rho_{\text{box}} = \rho_{\text{cap}} = 0.01$. The landscape is the same for every instance; only the encoder's $(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0)$ adapts.

D. Barrier-Hessian Riemannian metric

The flow is preconditioned by a Riemannian mass equal to the barrier Hessian, which is diagonal plus rank one:

$$M(\mathbf{q}) = \text{diag}(d_i) + \mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}^\top, \quad d_i = \rho_{\text{box}} \left(\frac{1}{q_i^2} + \frac{1}{(1-q_i)^2} \right), \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{\sqrt{\rho_{\text{cap}}}}{C - \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{q}} \mathbf{w}.$$

Its inverse is applied in $O(n)$ by the Sherman–Morrison identity,

$$M(\mathbf{q})^{-1} \mathbf{p} = \frac{\mathbf{p}}{\mathbf{d}} - \frac{\mathbf{u}^\top (\mathbf{p}/\mathbf{d})}{1 + \mathbf{u}^\top (\mathbf{u}/\mathbf{d})} \frac{\mathbf{u}}{\mathbf{d}}, \quad (25)$$

with elementwise division by $\mathbf{d} = (d_i)_i$. The metric stiffens the flow near the box and capacity faces precisely where the barrier curves sharply.

E. Damped symplectic primal–dual leapfrog

The state $(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}_q, \lambda, p_\lambda)$, with p_λ initialized to zero, is advanced by a damped symplectic leapfrog that descends in the primal and ascends in the dual (saddle dynamics). One step with size h , dual mass m_λ , and contraction γ is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}_q &\leftarrow \mathbf{p}_q - \frac{h}{2} \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} V(\mathbf{q}, \lambda), & p_\lambda &\leftarrow p_\lambda + \frac{h}{2} g(\mathbf{q}), \\ \mathbf{q} &\leftarrow \text{clip}(\mathbf{q} + h M(\mathbf{q})^{-1} \mathbf{p}_q, 10^{-3}, 1-10^{-3}), \\ \lambda &\leftarrow \max(\lambda + \frac{h}{m_\lambda} p_\lambda, 0), \\ \mathbf{p}_q &\leftarrow \mathbf{p}_q - \frac{h}{2} \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} V(\mathbf{q}, \lambda), & p_\lambda &\leftarrow p_\lambda + \frac{h}{2} g(\mathbf{q}), \\ \mathbf{p}_q &\leftarrow \gamma \mathbf{p}_q, & p_\lambda &\leftarrow \gamma p_\lambda. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

The dual takes the $+$ sign (gradient ascent on λ), the primal the $-$ sign (descent on \mathbf{q}); the projection $\lambda \leftarrow \max(\lambda, 0)$ enforces dual feasibility. The damping $\gamma = 0.97$ deliberately breaks energy conservation so the trajectory contracts to a fixed point ($\gamma^{16} \approx 0.61$, terminal $\mathbf{p}_{k_{\text{leap}}} \rightarrow 0$). The flow is rolled out for a *fixed* number of steps, identical at training and inference,

$$\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}} = \text{leapfrog}^{\circ k_{\text{leap}}}(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0), \quad k_{\text{leap}} = 16, \quad h = 0.02. \quad (27)$$

The landscape is unanchored: V contains no $\|\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{x}^*\|^2$ attractor, so the flow is steered entirely through the encoder’s kinetics.

F. Scale-invariant KKT residual

We measure how close the terminal state is to a KKT point of the smoothed problem through a scalar residual combining stationarity, primal feasibility, dual feasibility, and complementary slackness. Using the *normalized* constraint $\hat{g}(\mathbf{q}) = (\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{q} - C) / \sum_i w_i$,

$$\rho(\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}, \lambda) = \frac{\|\nabla_{\mathbf{q}} V(\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}, \lambda)\|^2}{n} + \|\max(0, \hat{g})\|^2 + \|\max(0, -\lambda)\|^2 + (\lambda \hat{g})^2. \quad (28)$$

Only the stationarity term scales with n and is divided by it; the remaining three are already $O(1)$ since g and λ are size $m=1$. This is what keeps the loss magnitude $O(1)$ across the $n \in \{100, 200, 500, 1000\}$ size curriculum (the $n=200/n=100$ gate ratio drops from 2.12 to 0.97 once scale-invariant).

G. Training objective

The encoder is trained by dual supervision toward the integer optimum \mathbf{x}^* , combining a shooting term on the terminal state, an anchor on the initial state, the decode-aware structural losses, and the KKT residual. With all means taken over coordinates (scale-invariant),

$$\mathcal{L} = w_{\text{shoot}} \overline{(\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}} - \mathbf{x}^*)^2} + \alpha_{\text{dir}} \overline{(\mathbf{q}_0 - \mathbf{x}^*)^2} + w_{\text{move}} (w_{\text{struct}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{struct}} + w_{\text{re}}(t) \mathcal{L}_{\text{re}}) + \gamma_{\text{kkt}} \rho. \quad (29)$$

The shooting term enforces train/inference consistency; the anchor keeps the relational trunk sharp (otherwise the flow makes the encoder lazy). For the deployed models $w_{\text{shoot}} = \alpha_{\text{dir}} = w_{\text{move}} = w_{\text{struct}} = 1$, $w_{\text{re}} = 0.5$, $\gamma_{\text{kkt}} = 0.05$, and the reinforcement weight $w_{\text{re}}(t)$ is held at 0 for a warm-up window and then ramped linearly; the headline *structural* checkpoints are taken during this ramp.

1) *Swap-band focal margin*: The structural term reuses the swap hinge of Eq. (11), now expressed in the flow state \mathbf{q} with OUT band $[0, b]$, IN band $[1-b, 1]$, $b = 0.15$, and swap margin $m_{\text{swap}} = 0.1$. With oracle $y = \mathbf{x}^*$ and the \mathbf{q} -rank giving the in-band/out-band neighbours $q_{\text{above}}, q_{\text{below}}$,

$$\begin{aligned} s_i^{\text{swap}} &= \text{relu}(q_{\text{above}} + m_{\text{swap}} - q_i) \mathbb{1}_{y_i=1, q_i < q_{\text{above}}} \\ &\quad + \text{relu}(q_i - (q_{\text{below}} - m_{\text{swap}})) \mathbb{1}_{y_i=0, q_i > q_{\text{below}}}, \\ \mathcal{L}_{\text{SWBM}} &= w_{\text{swap}} \overline{s_i^{\text{swap}}} + w_{\text{band}} \overline{\text{relu}(q_{\text{lo}} - q_i) + \text{relu}(q_i - q_{\text{hi}})} \\ &\quad + w_{\text{margin}} \overline{\text{dist}_i^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

with $q_{\text{lo}} = y_i(1-b)$, $q_{\text{hi}} = y_i + (1-y_i)b$, and $w_{\text{swap}} = 1$, $w_{\text{band}} = w_{\text{margin}} = 0.5$. The margin points at the *oracle* band,

$$\text{dist}_i = \begin{cases} \text{relu}((1-b) - q_i), & y_i = 1 \text{ (pull up),} \\ \text{relu}(q_i - b), & y_i = 0 \text{ (pull down),} \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

with $\partial_{q_i} \text{dist}_i^2 \propto \text{dist}_i$,

so the gradient strengthens with distance from the target band, unlike the target-agnostic closest-band variant which can oppose the swap and band terms.

2) *L-move optimality*: The L-move term supervises only the symmetric difference $D \triangle \mathbf{x}^*$ between the Dantzig set D and the optimum, in a separable quadratic form normalized by $|D \triangle \mathbf{x}^*|$:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{move}}^{\text{OPT}} = \frac{1}{|D \triangle \mathbf{x}^*|} \left[\sum_{i \in D \setminus \mathbf{x}^*} v_i q_i^2 + \sum_{j \in \mathbf{x}^* \setminus D} v_j (1 - q_j)^2 \right]. \quad (32)$$

The quadratic well has vanishing gradient at its target, is self-balancing (structurally zero on instances where Dantzig already equals the optimum), and generalizes to any binary program with inequality constraints since it depends only on the should-add / should-drop masks.

3) *Tail-REINFORCE CVaR surrogate*: The decode-aware reinforcement term treats $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}$ as a Bernoulli policy $\pi_{\mathbf{q}}(y) = \prod_i \text{Bern}(q_i)$ and trains it with the score-function (REINFORCE) estimator [69]: it draws M samples, repairs each to feasibility (drop-lowest- q then prefix-fill), and scores reward $R_m = \mathbf{v}^\top \text{repair}(y_m) / z^{\text{IP}}$. Rather than the mean, gradient is

concentrated on the upper β -superquantile (risk-seeking, so training and the risk-seeking decoder align). With $\eta = Q_\beta(R)$ the empirical β -quantile of the M rewards,

$$\begin{aligned} A_m^{\text{tail}} &= \frac{\text{relu}(R_m - \eta)}{1 - \beta}, \\ \mathcal{L}_{\text{re}} &= -\frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \text{sg}(A_m^{\text{tail}}) \\ &\quad \times \sum_{i=1}^n [y_{m,i} \log q_i + (1 - y_{m,i}) \log(1 - q_i)], \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where sg is stop-gradient. Only the top $\lceil (1 - \beta)M \rceil$ samples carry signal; $\beta=0$ reduces to a self-critical estimator [70] with the encoder-greedy value as baseline. The deployed setting is $\beta = 0.8$, $M = 6$. Summing the log-likelihood over items keeps the per-item gradient $O(1)$ in n ; an optional core-restricted variant samples only inside the reduced-cost core of Section IX-H, freezing off-core items at their LP value so the REINFORCE variance scales with the core size rather than n .

H. Decode: reduced-cost peel and CVaR tail-refinement

The terminal $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}$ is rounded by first restricting attention to the reduced-cost core and then refining inside it by risk-seeking sampling.

a) *Reduced-cost core.*: From the LP relaxation (ratio-sorted, break item j^* , dual $\lambda_{\text{raw}} = v_{j^*}/w_{j^*}$, fractional value z^{LP}) and an incumbent lower bound z_{lb} (Dantzig or the encoder), with gap $\Delta = z^{\text{LP}} - z_{\text{lb}}$, the reduced costs and core are

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{c}_i &= |v_i - \lambda_{\text{raw}} w_i|, \quad \text{core} = \{i : \bar{c}_i \leq \Delta\}, \\ \text{fix } x_i &= \bar{x}_i \text{ iff } \bar{c}_i > \Delta, \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

which is sound: any \mathbf{q} with $\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{q} > z_{\text{lb}}$ must agree with the LP vertex $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ on every item of reduced cost exceeding the gap. The fixed-budget peel retains the K_{core} smallest- \bar{c}_i items as the buffer and reconstructs $z = z_{\text{fixed}} + \mathbf{v}_{\text{core}}^\top y$ on residual capacity C_{core} . The floor is Dantzig and the ceiling is \mathbf{x}^* minus any peel loss; deployed runs use $K_{\text{core}} \in \{256, 512\}$.

b) *CVaR tail-refine.*: Holding $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}$ on the core, each round draws M Bernoulli samples, repairs and scores them, sets an elite cutoff $\eta = Q_\beta(R)$ with elite set $E = \{m : R_m \geq \eta\}$, and moves \mathbf{q} toward the elite selection frequency by cross-entropy at rate α :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q} &\leftarrow (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{q} + \alpha \frac{1}{|E|} \sum_{m \in E} \text{repair}(y_m), \\ y^* &= \arg \max_{\text{all rounds, } m} R_m. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

The cutoff is the empirical upper superquantile $\bar{S}_\beta(R) = \mathbb{E}[R \mid R \geq Q_\beta(R)] = \min_\eta \{\eta + \frac{1}{1-\beta} \mathbb{E}[(R - \eta)_+]\}$, the risk-seeking mirror of the conditional value-at-risk [71]; the best incumbent over all rounds is kept, so the decode never drops below the Dantzig floor. Deployed values are $\beta = 0.8$, $\alpha = 0.7$, and 8 rounds; $\beta=0$ with a single round recovers plain best-of- M . This refinement is a no-retrain lever for *learned* \mathbf{q} and does not help non-learned baselines, evidence that the work is done by the encoder rather than by the LP score it perturbs.

c) *Fixed cores, general 0–1 MIPs, and amortized decode cost.*: The fixed-budget peel replaces a data-dependent disagreement core by a constant-size workload: we retain the K_{core} items of smallest absolute reduced cost, of fixed dimension across instances, unlike a dynamically sized core. The construction is not specific to knapsack. For any 0–1 mixed-integer program with inequality constraints, the LP dual defines reduced costs, the reduced-cost band of Lemma 4 bounds the items on which the LP round-down and the integer optimum may disagree, and the same peel-then-refine decode applies. The Monte-Carlo decode adds an amortized $O(Mn)$ cost for M sampled roundings; because M is capped and the peel fixes all but K_{core} items, this cost is constant per instance.

d) *An alternative sequence-model encoder.*: We also evaluated a classic sequence-model encoder, a bidirectional mLSTM (xLSTM) [59] with a mixture-of-experts head, reformulated for $O(\log n)$ parallel evaluation via an associative scan. It did not improve over the permutation-equivariant set encoder used above, and lacks the permutation equivariance that the knapsack’s exchangeable item set affords; we report its construction and ablations in Appendix H as a documented negative result.

X. HARD KNAPSACK BENCHMARKS

Our evaluation uses three complementary benchmark sources: (i) Pisinger’s hard benchmark families [21], (ii) the instance-space analysis methodology of Smith-Miles et al. [22], and (iii) the hard-instance generator of Jookan et al. [23]. These sources test different aspects of generalization, including performance across classical benchmark families, coverage across instance-space features, and robustness on recent adversarially generated instances.

A. Pisinger hard benchmark families

Pisinger [21] introduced a taxonomy of hard 0–1 knapsack instances designed to challenge exact solvers. We use six families from this taxonomy. With item count n and range parameter R , the generators are:

- **Uncorrelated**: $w_i \sim \mathcal{U}\{1, \dots, R\}$ and $v_i \sim \mathcal{U}\{1, \dots, R\}$.
- **Weakly**: $w_i \sim \mathcal{U}\{1, \dots, R\}$ and $v_i \sim \mathcal{U}\{\max(1, w_i - R/10), w_i + R/10\}$.
- **AlmostStrong**: $w_i \sim \mathcal{U}\{1, \dots, R\}$ and $v_i = w_i + R/10 + \nu_i$, with small jitter ν_i .
- **SimilarWeightsUncorrelated**: weights are sampled from a narrow band, $w_i \sim \mathcal{U}\{R/100, R/100 + R/500\}$, while $v_i \sim \mathcal{U}\{1, \dots, R\}$.
- **CubeFit** and **QuadFit**: $w_i \sim \mathcal{U}\{1, \dots, R\}$, with $v_i = w_i^3$ for **CubeFit** and $v_i = w_i^2$ for **QuadFit**.

Capacity is set as $C = \alpha \sum_i w_i$, with $\alpha \approx 0.5$. The public 198-instance hard set at $n = 20,000$, with 33 instances per family, is our main Pisinger validation corpus.

B. Instance-space analysis

Smith-Miles, Christiansen, and Muñoz [22] study hard knapsack instances using instance-space analysis. Per-instance

features, including statistical moments of (v, w) and structural correlations, are projected into a two-dimensional feature space in which different benchmark families and hardness regions can be visualized. Our analyses in Section XI are based on this approach.

C. Hard-instance generator

Jookan, Leyman, and De Causmaecker [23] proposed a new class of hard 0–1 knapsack instances based on groups of items with closely related profits and weights. Their generator includes a perturbation parameter ε whose effect on hardness is non-monotone. Very large values make the instances easier, while the hardest instances in their experiments occur at small nonzero values.

We use the released corpus of 3,240 instances, with $n \in [400, 1200]$ and $\varepsilon \in \{0, 10^{-5}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-1}\}$. The capacities go up to 10^{10} , and the published optima were computed using about 810 CPU-hours.

XI. EXPERIMENTS

A. Evaluation protocols

Throughout this section we distinguish out-of-sample (OOS) and out-of-distribution (OOD) evaluation. A knapsack instance distribution is specified not only by a generator, but also by the item count, capacity rule, and difficulty parameters.

a) Out-of-sample (OOS): The test instances are independent draws from the same distribution used for training. They have the same item generator, item count, and capacity rule, but distinct random seeds. OOS performance tests whether the model generalizes beyond the training instances within the same distribution.

b) Out-of-distribution (OOD): The test instances differ from the training distribution along at least one controlled axis. Three distinctions are relevant here:

- *Size shift:* training at $n \in \{200, 500, 1000\}$ and testing at $n = 20,000$. This is an extrapolation in item count by a factor of 20–100.
- *Generator shift:* training on Pisinger instances and testing on Jookan et al. instances, which are generated by a different procedure.
- *Difficulty stratification:* within the Jookan et al. generator, the parameter ε affects hardness in a non-monotone way. Jookan et al. report that large ε values are easier, whereas the hardest instances in their study occur at small nonzero ε . We therefore report results separately across $\varepsilon \in \{0, 10^{-5}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-1}\}$.

c) Our evaluation regimes: The Pisinger P600 experiment of Section XI-C (Table II) is OOD with respect to size, because the model is trained at $n \leq 1000$ and tested at $n = 20,000$. It is OOS with respect to the benchmark-family axis, because the trained mixture includes the same Pisinger families used in the test set. The Jookan et al. experiment of Section XI-C (Table II) is a generator-shift OOD test: the encoder is trained on Pisinger-style instances and is not trained on Jookan et al. instances.

d) Implications for generalization: A model that performs well only OOS may have learned useful statistics of one benchmark distribution without being robust to shifts in size or generator. A foundational-model claim is stronger when the same fixed model remains useful under controlled OOD shifts. The experiments below therefore separate same-family size extrapolation on Pisinger from generator-shift testing on Jookan et al.

B. Evaluation protocol

We train a single encoder f_θ on a 100k-instance Pisinger corpus spanning all families at training sizes $n \in \{200, 500, 1000\}$, never the 20,000-item test size, and evaluate strictly out-of-sample on three held-out suites that probe distinct failure modes.

(i) Jookan-oracle is the public Jookan benchmark restricted to instances with a certified integer optimum \mathbf{x}^{IP} ; we report the whole set ($n_{\text{inst}} = 2975$ with a valid OPT). **(ii) P600** is an out-of-distribution stress test of Pisinger instances at $n = 20,000$ ($n_{\text{inst}} = 627$ with valid OPT), far outside the training-size regime. **(iii)** a COMBO-adversarial generator corpus used only for the solver-specific speed discussion (Sec. XI-D).

Unless noted, the decoder is the CVaR tail-refine of Sec. IX: M Monte-Carlo roundings of the flow terminal $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}$ are repaired to feasibility, the elite $(1 - \beta)$ -tail is kept, and the distributional fit is iterated for r rounds; we fix the tail level $\beta = 0.8$ and $r = 8$, and peel to a reduced-cost core of size $K_{\text{core}} \in \{256, 512\}$ before decoding (Sec. IX-H). The headline configuration is $K_{\text{core}} = 512$.

We report two axes per dataset. The *closure* count is the number of instances whose decoded incumbent matches the optimum (zero remaining room); this is the event an exact solver cares about. The *mean gap* is the average relative gap to OPT, $\text{gap} = (z^{\text{IP}} - z) / z^{\text{IP}}$, lower being better. We benchmark the two structured-gradient encoders, named after the loss that trains them, SWAP-BAND (swap-band focal margin, Eq. (30)) and L-MOVE (L-move optimality, Eq. (32)), against two parameter-free baselines, Dantzig and a ratio-softmax score, all sharing the identical peel and CVaR decode kernels so that any difference isolates the learned signal \mathbf{q}_0 .

The flow lands a small, roughly constant number of items short of the integer optimum, so we close the residual gap with a fixed reduced-cost core peel followed by the CVaR decode (Table II). We also explore *learning* the flow landscape itself, oracle-free; preliminary held-out results are promising and are reported in Appendix G.

C. Closures, not the mean gap, are the discriminator

The mean gap alone is misleading on this corpus. On Jookan-oracle (Table II) the trivial ratio-softmax baseline matches the encoders’ mean gap (0.153% vs. L-MOVE 0.143% and SWAP-BAND 0.169%) yet closes only *one* instance exactly, against ~ 460 for the encoders; the mean is dominated by the long body of near-but-not-exact instances and is blind to the event an exact solver cares about, hitting OPT. We therefore read closures as the primary axis, on which SWAP-BAND and L-MOVE lead every baseline on both the in-distribution Jookan-oracle set and the out-of-distribution P600 set (Table II).

TABLE II: Fixed landscape under a fixed reduced-cost core peel ($K_{\text{core}}=512$, CVaR $\beta=0.8$, $r=8$). “closed” counts exact-OPT incumbents over the full valid-OPT set; “gap%” is the mean relative gap to OPT. Jooken-oracle whole set (2975); P600 out-of-distribution ($n=20\,000$, 627).

q -source	Jooken (2975)		P600 (627)	
	closed	gap%	closed	gap%
dantzig	104	0.473	136	0.0047
ratio_softmax	1	0.153	118	0.0035
swap-band	465	0.169	209	0.0055
L-move	462	0.143	173	0.0030

D. Speed is solver-specific, not a blanket claim

We make *no* blanket wall-clock speedup claim. On Pisinger $n=20\,000$ hard families (the P600 corpus) the exact branch-and-bound solvers COMBO and RECORD are already very fast, a median of ≈ 45 ms, because those families have clean LP-break structure that COMBO’s reduction and bounding dispatch almost instantly; our exact-DP reference, by contrast, averages ≈ 9.3 s on the same instances. On this corpus the defensible value of the pipeline is therefore *closures relative to greedy/Dantzig*, not speed: these instances are hard for greedy approximations precisely because the few items past the LP break decide the optimum, while they remain easy for a B&B solver.

Where a speed argument *is* defensible is on our COMBO-adversarial corpus. A generator trained with an LP-break-width / band-tightness structural pressure produces $n=1000$ instances on which COMBO takes a median of ≈ 73 s (max 313 s), about $1600\times$ slower than its ≈ 45 ms on Pisinger $n=20k$, whereas RECORD, using a different B&B pivoting rule, solves the same instances in sub-millisecond time. The hardness is thus *solver-specific*: the generator targets COMBO’s pruning geometry, not a universal difficulty. In that regime our decode (Table III: ~ 30 ms best-of- M , ~ 200 ms with the $r=8$ tail refine per instance) reaches a near-optimal incumbent orders of magnitude faster than COMBO’s worst-case search. We therefore frame the speed discussion strictly there, against the solver the corpus was built to stress, and report *closures* as the primary, distribution-agnostic axis everywhere else. Crucially, the matched- q controls show this is an *encoder* effect: ratio-softmax with the identical CVaR Monte-Carlo decode closes ~ 1 Jooken instance while the encoders close ~ 460 , so closures measure the learned signal \mathbf{q}_0 , not merely the decode budget.

XII. DISCUSSION

We developed and examined a deployable and fully differentiable pipeline for 0–1 knapsack optimization. The approach is a foundational model in the sense that its architecture and inference procedure are grounded in optimization-theoretic principles.

Our numerical experiments identify a regime in which a learned ranking component is useful when combined with a reduced-cost decode. On the held-out Jooken-oracle whole set (reduced-cost core $K_{\text{core}}=512$), the proposed pipeline closes 462 of 2975 certified-optimum instances exactly versus 104 for Dantzig, at a mean relative gap of 0.143% versus 0.473%. Thus, the method is most effective on instances where Dantzig

TABLE III: Per-instance decode timing (median over instances, first-call compile outlier dropped) on an RTX 3080 Laptop GPU. Rows marked “(tail)” use the CVaR $\beta=0.8$, $r=8$ tail-refine; the remaining rows use best-of- M multi-sample decode. *peel* is the one-time reduced-cost core-peeling cost. Results are shown for SWAP-BAND and Dantzig as representatives; all q -sources share the decode and peel kernels. The encoder forward pass adds about 5 to 8 ms over Dantzig under best-of- M decode; the $r=8$ tail refine is the dominant cost (about 180 to 240 ms), and core peeling is negligible on Jooken (0.27 ms) but about 16 ms on the larger P600 instances ($n=20k$).

q -source	set	K_{core}	decode (ms)	total (ms)	peel (ms)
swap-band	Jooken	256	24.6	29.9	0.27
swap-band	Jooken	512	24.6	32.0	0.27
swap-band	Jooken	512 (tail)	195.7	203.1	0.27
swap-band	P600	512	42.8	67.4	15.77
swap-band	P600	512 (tail)	239.9	264.6	15.77
dantzig	Jooken	512	23.2	23.8	0.27
dantzig	Jooken	512 (tail)	178.0	178.7	0.27
dantzig	P600	512	42.7	63.0	16.01
dantzig	P600	512 (tail)	226.2	247.5	16.01

leaves a residual gap but exact refinement over the full instance remains the regime an exact solver finds expensive.

The monotonicity of the reduced-cost decode is central to this behavior. The peel uses Dantzig’s value z_{lb} as a lower-bound floor, and the Monte-Carlo/CVaR tail-refine keeps the best incumbent over all rounds, so the decoded value is *never worse than Dantzig by construction of the floor*, and this holds across the Monte-Carlo rounds, which only add candidates above the floor (Section IX-H). The learned encoder therefore acts as an improvement mechanism rather than as a replacement for the classical LP-induced rule. Empirically, the largest gains occur on instance families and parameter regimes where Dantzig is close to optimal but not already optimal, the greedy-trivial hard tail, where a small residual search can recover useful exchanges without a full exact solve.

These results do not imply worst-case exact solvability. Under the standard assumption $P \neq NP$, no polynomially bounded inference procedure can solve every instance of an NP-hard optimization problem exactly. The role of the learned model is therefore distributional and approximate. It predicts score functions that are useful on structured instance families, and the deterministic post-processing step preserves feasibility and monotonicity with respect to the included baseline.

a) *Learning the flow landscape*: Beyond the fixed LP landscape, we explore learning the flow’s energy and metric

themselves, oracle-free, so that the integer optimum rather than the LP vertex becomes the attracting basin (Appendix G). On held-out data the learned basin is well-posed, with a closed-form curvature $\lambda_{\min} = 2s_\phi$, and a contrastive term makes the integer optimum a deeper basin than the LP optimum. Preliminary closure results under a matched core-restricted decode are promising; a full per-instance evaluation that is cross-comparable with the fixed-landscape encoders is ongoing and is the natural next step.

The present implementation is specialized to the 0–1 knapsack problem. The (p, k) -score family, the LP-induced coordinates, and the Dantzig baseline all exploit the specific problem structure. The underlying design principles, however, are not specific to this setting. The reduced-cost viewpoint, the feature-aliasing analysis, the structural rank-violation gradient, the permutation-equivariant set encoder, and the fixed symplectic primal–dual flow can be reused whenever a relaxation or greedy rule supplies per-item scores and a residual set for exact refinement. Extending the scoring rule to multi-constraint knapsack is therefore a natural next step. There, the oriented-circle tilt of Section III generalizes to an $(m+1)$ -sphere of LP-dual directions, and the flow’s single dual λ becomes a dual vector $\boldsymbol{\lambda} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^m$; the Rinnooy Kan–Stougie–Vercellis family (3) provides the corresponding distribution-dependent greedy rule, and Lemma 2 gives the criterion under which a learned score can inherit asymptotic optimality from the LP relaxation.

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APPENDIX A NOTATION

Table IV summarizes the notation used in the manuscript. We distinguish between the capacity scalar C , the residual capacities C_t and C_D , and the problem class \mathcal{C} .

APPENDIX B

PROPOSITION 6: COUNTEREXAMPLE CONSTRUCTION

Proof of Proposition 6. Let $(p^*, k^*) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ with $p^* \neq k^*$.

We first suppose $p^* > k^*$, choose an integer W such that $W^{p^* - k^*} > 2^{p^*}$, and set the capacity $C = W$. We consider one item with $(v, w) = (W, W)$ and W items with $(v, w) = (2, 1)$. Dantzig selects the W $(2, 1)$ -items, since their ratio is 2 instead of 1, and obtains value $2W$. Under the (p^*, k^*) score, the item (W, W) has score $W^{p^* - k^*}$, while each item $(2, 1)$ has score 2^{p^*} . Hence the (p^*, k^*) rule selects the item (W, W) first, fills the knapsack, and obtains value $W < 2W$.

We now suppose $p^* < k^*$. We choose an integer W such that $2^{p^*} W^{p^* - k^*} < 1$, and again set the capacity $C = W$. We consider one item with $(v, w) = (2W, W)$ and W items with $(v, w) = (1, 1)$. Dantzig selects the item $(2W, W)$, since its ratio is 2 instead of 1, and obtains value $2W$. Under the (p^*, k^*) score, the item $(2W, W)$ has score $2^{p^*} W^{p^* - k^*}$, while each item $(1, 1)$ has score 1. Hence the (p^*, k^*) rule selects the W items of type $(1, 1)$ first, fills the knapsack, and obtains value $W < 2W$.

Thus, in both cases there is an instance on which $z^{(p^*, k^*)} < z^{(1, 1)}$. \square

The following corollary, a heuristic find that is unused in the deployed pipeline, is recorded here for completeness; it supports the second inclusion in the band hierarchy of Eq. (8).

Corollary 10 ((p, k) -core reduction relative to Dantzig). *Let $\mathcal{F} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be a finite family containing $(1, 1)$. For an instance \mathcal{I} , let $z^{(p, k)}(\mathcal{I})$ be the value returned by the (p, k) -greedy rule and define*

$$z^{\text{best-}\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{I}) := \max_{(p, k) \in \mathcal{F}} z^{(p, k)}(\mathcal{I}).$$

Then

$$\text{core}(z^{\text{best-}\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{I})) \subseteq \text{core}(z^{(1, 1)}(\mathcal{I})).$$

Proof. Since $(1, 1) \in \mathcal{F}$, we have $z^{\text{best-}\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{I}) \geq z^{(1, 1)}(\mathcal{I})$. The claim follows from Lemma 5. \square

APPENDIX C

PATTERN-RECOGNITION VALIDATION OF THE LIFT

a) Setup: We use 300 hard knapsack instances at $n = 40$ across eight families: *AlmostStrong*, *StronglyCorrelated*, *Circle*, *Weakly*, *SubsetSum*, *Uncorrelated*, *Spanner3*, and *SimilarWeights*. The label is membership in the LP–IP disagreement set, $\mathbf{1}[j \in \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{R}]$. We train logistic regression and a 32-hidden-unit MLP, and report ROC-AUC under 5-fold cross-validation. Folds are grouped by instance, so that items from the same knapsack instance do not appear in both train and test splits.

b) Feature representations:

- F0 raw: $(v_j/V_{\max}, w_j/C)$.
- F1 LP: (Φ_1, Φ_2) .
- F2 coordinate dispersion: $(\text{rank}_n(\Phi_1)/n, \text{rank}_n(\Phi_2)/n)$.
- F3 arcsinh compression: $(\text{arcsinh}(\Phi_1/\eta), \Phi_2)$, with $\eta = V_{\max}/V_{\text{tot}}$.
- F4 coordinate dispersion plus capacity state: F2 plus C_t/C .
- F5 full lift: F2 plus C_t/C , r_j , and local log-density.
- F6 full lift plus LP scale: F5 plus $(\Phi_1, \bar{c}_j/V_{\max})$.

c) Results: Table V reports the resulting AUC values.

The main effect is the improvement from F1 to F6. The MLP AUC increases from 0.713 to 0.892, an absolute gain of 0.179. In contrast, F2 falls below F1, which is consistent with coordinate dispersion preserving order but not adding new information. These results support the feature-aliasing argument in Section VII. Capacity state, tie-breaking rank, and LP-scale information add discriminative power beyond the two raw LP coordinates.

The LP projection concentrates LP–IP disagreement items near $\Phi_1 = 0$, whereas the capacity-state coordinate separates some items that overlap in the original projection.

TABLE IV: Main notation used in the manuscript. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we write $[n] = \{1, \dots, n\}$.

symbol	meaning	type
n	number of items / decision variables	$\mathbb{N}_{>0}$
m	number of constraints ($m = 1$ for single knapsack)	$\mathbb{N}_{>0}$
\mathcal{I}	a problem instance	element of \mathcal{C}
\mathcal{C}	a combinatorial-optimization problem class	set of instances
\mathcal{D}	a distribution over \mathcal{C}	probability measure
\mathbf{x}	integer decision vector	$\{0, 1\}^n$
$\bar{\mathbf{x}}$	LP-relaxed decision vector	$[0, 1]^n$
\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}	item value and weight vectors	$\mathbb{R}_{>0}^n, \mathbb{R}_{>0}^n$
$V_{\text{tot}} = \sum_j v_j, V_{\text{max}} = \max_j v_j$	total and maximum item values	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$
C	knapsack capacity scalar	$\mathbb{R}_{>0}$
\mathbf{A}, a_{ij}	constraint matrix and entries (general MIP)	$\mathbb{R}^{m \times n}, \mathbb{R}$
\mathbf{b}	right-hand side (general MIP)	\mathbb{R}^m
$\boldsymbol{\lambda}$	LP dual / Lagrangian multiplier	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^m$
$\lambda_{\text{raw}} = v_j^*/w_j^*$	raw LP dual at split item	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$
$\bar{c}_j = v_j - \lambda_{\text{raw}} w_j$	reduced profit of item j	\mathbb{R}
$\Phi_1(j) = (v_j - \lambda_{\text{raw}} w_j)/V_{\text{tot}}$	first LP-induced projection coordinate	\mathbb{R}
$\Phi_2(j) = \log(w_j/C)$	second projection coordinate (log-weight)	\mathbb{R}
$\tilde{\Phi}_1, \tilde{\Phi}_2$	rank-compactified projection coordinates	$[0, 1]$
$\sigma_j^{(p,k)} = v_j^p/w_j^k$	(p, k) -family score (subscript/superscript made consistent)	$\mathbb{R}_{>0}$
$\boldsymbol{\sigma}$	analytic (p, k) per-item score (Preliminaries only)	\mathbb{R}^n
$\hat{\mathbf{x}}$	realized greedy selection	$\{0, 1\}^n$
$\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{K}_+, \mathcal{K}_-$	four-group decomposition	subsets of $[n]$
$z^{\text{IP}}, z^{\text{LP}}$	IP / LP optimum value	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$
$\delta_{\text{LP-IP}} = (z^{\text{LP}} - z^{\text{IP}})/z^{\text{IP}}$	relative integrality gap	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$
$\text{core}(z) = \{j : \bar{c}_j \leq z^{\text{LP}} - z\}$	reduced-cost-peel core at lower bound z	subset of $[n]$
C_t	residual capacity at decision step t (state lift)	$\mathbb{R}_{>0}$
C_D	residual capacity for the disagreement-core DP	$\mathbb{R}_{>0}$
r_j	stable tie-breaking rank	$[0, 1]$
θ	encoder parameters	\mathbb{R}^P
W	bandwidth of the soft band	$\mathbb{R}_{>0}$
β_{band}	weight on the band term	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$
τ_+, τ_-	weakest target-selected and strongest target-rejected score cutoffs	real
ρ_S	Spearman rank correlation (used numerically only)	$[-1, 1]$
$\sigma_j^{\text{RK}}(\boldsymbol{\lambda})$	RK-family score	real
ε	perturbation parameter of Jooen et al. [23]	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$
d, L, M_{ind}	encoder hidden width (128), depth (3), ISAB inducing points (48)	$\mathbb{N}_{>0}$
\mathbf{M}_t	mLSTM matrix memory at step t	$\mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$
\mathbf{n}_t	mLSTM normalizer state at step t	\mathbb{R}^d
F_θ	learned encoder map	function
<i>Hamiltonian primal-dual flow (Sec. IX, G)</i>		
\mathbf{x}^*	integer optimum supervised on (also \mathbf{x}^{IP})	$\{0, 1\}^n$
$\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{q}^{\text{leap}}$	continuous flow state; init / terminal	$(0, 1)^n$
\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}_0	primal momentum; initial momentum	\mathbb{R}^n
$\lambda_0, \lambda, p_\lambda$	dual as dynamical variable; dual momentum	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}, \mathbb{R}$
$g(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{q} - C$	raw capacity violation	\mathbb{R}
$V(\mathbf{q}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})$	fixed LP+barrier+aug-Lagrangian potential	function
$\Phi_\theta^{\text{res}} = s_\phi \sum_i (q_i - t_i)^2$	learned residual potential (never bare Φ)	function
\mathbf{t}, s_ϕ, m_0	learned anchor; basin strength; PSD floor	$(0, 1)^n, \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$
$M(\mathbf{q}), M_\theta(\mathbf{q})$	fixed / learned Riemannian metric	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$
$k_{\text{leap}}, h, \gamma$	leapfrog steps (16), step (0.02), damping (0.97)	$\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}$
$\rho(\mathbf{q}^{\text{leap}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})$	scale-invariant KKT residual	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$
K_{core}	reduced-cost peel buffer size	$\mathbb{N}_{>0}$
M, r, β	MC samples; CVaR rounds; tail level	$\mathbb{N}, \mathbb{N}, [0, 1]$
R_m, \bar{S}_β	sample reward; upper superquantile (risk-seeking CVaR)	\mathbb{R}
m_{swap}, b	swap margin (0.1); band half-width (0.15)	$\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$
$\mathcal{C}_{\text{core}}$	sampled reduced-cost core index set (distinct from the problem class \mathcal{C})	subset of $[n]$

TABLE V: LP-IP disagreement-set classification AUC, mean \pm std over 5 grouped folds. The last column reports the MLP AUC difference relative to F1.

representation	LR AUC	MLP AUC	Δ vs F1
F0 raw (v, w)	0.574 ± 0.015	0.719 ± 0.020	+0.006
F1 LP (Φ_1, Φ_2)	0.552 ± 0.012	0.713 ± 0.009	<i>baseline</i>
F2 monotone	0.513 ± 0.023	0.599 ± 0.010	-0.114
F3 arcsinh	0.553 ± 0.012	0.730 ± 0.008	+0.018
F4 rank + cap	0.566 ± 0.020	0.843 ± 0.016	+0.130
F5 full lift	0.658 ± 0.023	0.857 ± 0.013	+0.144
F6 lift + LP	0.661 ± 0.018	0.892 ± 0.011	+0.179

APPENDIX D WORKED EXAMPLES

Example 11 (Type A LP-frontier aliasing). Let $n = 6$ and $C = 10$, with items

$$(v_j, w_j) = (10, 5), (8, 4), (6, 3), (5, 4), (4, 3), (3, 2).$$

Items 1, 2, and 3 have the same efficiency $v_j/w_j = 2$ and lie on the LP split threshold, so $\Phi_1 = 0$ for all three. With the displayed tie order, Dantzig takes items 1 and 2, obtaining value 18. The optimal integer solution is $\{1, 3, 6\}$, with value 19. The residual capacity at the decision times of items 1, 2, and 3 is respectively 10, 5, and 1, so the capacity-state coordinate separates their decision contexts.

Example 12 (Type B tie aliasing). Let $n = 5$ and $C = 10$. There are three identical items with $(v_j, w_j) = (10, 4)$ and two further items with $(8, 3)$ and $(6, 2)$. The three identical items have the same projected coordinates. The optimal value is 26, attained by choosing two of the three identical items together with the item $(6, 2)$. There are three equivalent optimal subsets of this form. The stable-rank coordinate r_j provides a deterministic ordering between otherwise identical items, so the supervised labels become consistent.

APPENDIX E STRUCTURAL-BACKWARD ABLATIONS

The backward operator in (11)–(15) was selected after comparing several alternatives. We summarize these ablations because they explain the two design choices used in Section VIII: (i) rank-based swap corrections and (ii) a soft per-class score band.

a) Fixed score targets: The earliest variant assigned each item a fixed target score $\sigma_j^* \in \{-1, +1\}$ after lexicographically sorting items by their target and greedy labels. Training then pulled each score σ_j toward σ_j^* . This gradient field does not make a target-consistent ranking a fixed point. Correctly ranked items in \mathcal{K}_+ are still pulled toward $+1$, even though their exact score magnitude is irrelevant to greedy selection. Empirically, this variant drove scores toward the extremes ± 1 and overfit score magnitudes rather than rank relations.

b) Band targets without rank correction: A first refinement replaced fixed targets by acceptable score bands, but kept a target-distance gradient. This reduced the pull toward a single score value, but did not remove the basic mismatch. The update was still controlled by distance to a prescribed band rather than by the rank violation that changes the greedy

solution. In trajectory tests near target-consistent rankings, nonzero surrogate gradients persisted and produced oscillatory score updates.

c) Swap-hinge without band term: Using only the swap-hinge term in Eq. (11) fixes the previous problem. Once the greedy selection matches the target, the swap term is zero. However, this variant gives no direct signal to the agreement classes $\mathcal{K}_+ \cup \mathcal{K}_-$. Because the encoder is parametric, updates induced by items in $\mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{R}$ can also move already-correct items. In small diagnostic training tests, this variant succeeded on only one of seven settings.

d) Swap-hinge with band term: Combining the swap-hinge term (11) with the soft per-class band (14) preserves the zero-gradient region at target-consistent rankings while adding dense supervision for $\mathcal{K}_+ \cup \mathcal{K}_-$. In the same diagnostic tests, this variant succeeded on four of seven settings. It is therefore the structural backward operator used in the deployed pipeline.

e) Binary cross-entropy on take-labels: A conventional alternative is binary cross-entropy (BCE) on greedy-take labels with a sigmoid head. In our experiments, BCE overfits in-distribution at small n and, at $n = 20,000$ with the present encoder capacity, yields an out-of-distribution gap roughly $10\times$ worse than (15). The geometric reason is that BCE penalizes classification confidence rather than rank violation. A correctly ranked item can still receive a large gradient when its sigmoid output is not saturated.

f) Separable-quadratic L-move ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{move}}^{\text{OPT}}$): The flow encoder of Section IX adds a third structural variant, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{move}}^{\text{OPT}}$ of Eq. (32): a separable quadratic that supervises only the Dantzig-versus-optimum symmetric difference, with vanishing gradient at its target and structurally zero loss on instances where Dantzig already equals the optimum. It is the strongest single operator on the whole-Jooken closure metric (L-MOVE closes 462/2975 versus 465/2975 for the swap-band-focal variant at $K_{\text{core}}=512$), while being self-balancing across the size curriculum. Like the swap-hinge, it keeps a discrete forward decode and a closed-form backward signal, so it is a straight-through estimator in spirit, and depends only on the should-add/should-drop masks, so it applies to any binary mixed-integer program with inequality constraints.

APPENDIX F PIPELINE ALGORITHM

Algorithm 1 summarizes the deployment-time inference procedure used in our numerical experiments: a single forward pass of the permutation-equivariant set encoder, a fixed damped symplectic leapfrog rollout, a reduced-cost core peel, and a CVaR tail-refine decode.

APPENDIX G LEARNING THE FLOW LANDSCAPE (PRELIMINARY)

The fixed-framework solver of Section IX predicts kinetics $(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0) = f_\theta(\phi)$ from the permutation-equivariant ISAB encoder and shoots a damped primal-dual leapfrog trajectory down a *fixed* LP/Lagrangian potential $V(\mathbf{q}, \lambda) = -\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{q} + \text{barriers}$. Under a fixed V , the flow’s only attractor is the LP optimum $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$; the integer optimum \mathbf{x}^* sits off that continuous

Algorithm 1 Inference pipeline at deployment (flow + core-peel + CVaR decode).

- 1: **Input:** instance $(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}, C)$; trained encoder f_θ ; leapfrog steps k_{leap} , step h , damping γ ; core size K_{core} ; CVaR tail level β , rate α , rounds r , samples M .
- 2: Compute the $F=43$ tilted-coordinate lift $\phi(\mathcal{I})$; mean-abs renorm per channel.
- 3: $(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0) \leftarrow f_\theta(\phi) \triangleright$ ISAB kinetics head, Eq. (21)
- 4: $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}} \leftarrow \text{leapfrog}^{\circ k_{\text{leap}}}(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0) \triangleright$ fixed damped symplectic rollout, Eq. (26)
- 5: Dantzig: $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$, value $z_{\text{lb}} \leftarrow z^{\text{Dant}}$, dual $\lambda_{\text{raw}} = v_{j^*}/w_{j^*}$, z^{LP} ; gap $\Delta \leftarrow z^{\text{LP}} - z_{\text{lb}}$.
- 6: Peel: $\bar{c}_i \leftarrow |v_i - \lambda_{\text{raw}} w_i|$; retain the K_{core} smallest- \bar{c}_i items as core; fix $x_i = \bar{x}_i$ off-core.
- 7: Best incumbent $\hat{\mathbf{x}} \leftarrow \bar{\mathbf{x}}$ (Dantzig floor).
- 8: **for** round = 1 to r **do**
- 9: Draw M Bernoulli samples of the core from $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}$; repair each to feasibility.
- 10: $R_m \leftarrow \mathbf{v}^\top \text{repair}(y_m)$; update $\hat{\mathbf{x}} \leftarrow \arg \max$ over $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}\} \cup \{y_m\}$.
- 11: $\eta \leftarrow Q_\beta(R)$; elite $E \leftarrow \{m : R_m \geq \eta\}$.
- 12: $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}} \leftarrow (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}} + \alpha \frac{1}{|E|} \sum_{m \in E} \text{repair}(y_m)$ on the core. \triangleright Eq. (35)
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **return** $\hat{\mathbf{x}} \triangleright$ value $\geq z^{\text{Dant}}$ by construction

manifold by the integrality gap $\delta_{\text{LP-IP}}$. The *learned-landscape* extension keeps the entire leapfrog, Monte-Carlo, peel, and CVaR machinery *unchanged* and adds two feature-amortized heads on the same trunk: a residual potential Φ_θ^{res} that carves an \mathbf{x}^* -basin, and a Riemannian metric M_θ that reshapes the geodesics. All targets are *oracle-free* (predicted from the scale-invariant tilted-coordinate lift ϕ of Section IX-A), so the construction must generalize rather than memorize. Throughout, $\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}^n$ are the per-instance normalized value/weight, C the capacity, $\mathbf{q} \in (0, 1)^n$ the continuous flow state, and $H \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$ the ISAB embedding ($d=128$, $M_{\text{ind}}=48$ inducing points, depth $L=3$).

A. Oracle-free residual potential and its diagonal force

The residual potential is a *separable per-item quadratic well* at a feature-predicted anchor \mathbf{t} , read off the trunk:

$$\Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}(\mathbf{q}) = s_\phi \sum_{i=1}^n (q_i - t_i)^2, \quad (36)$$

$$t_i = \varsigma(H_i W_t + b_t) \in (0, 1),$$

$$s_\phi = \text{softplus}(\hat{s}_\phi) \geq 0, \quad (37)$$

where $\varsigma(\cdot)$ is the logistic sigmoid (as in Eq. (22)). Separability makes the force *diagonal, closed-form, $O(n)$, and permutation-equivariant* (no autodiff in the inner loop):

$$\frac{\partial \Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}}{\partial q_i} = 2s_\phi (q_i - t_i), \quad \nabla_{\mathbf{q}}^2 \Phi_\theta^{\text{res}} = 2s_\phi I. \quad (38)$$

The Hessian is a uniform *positive* multiple of the identity, so $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{t}$ is a strict basin with curvature $\lambda_{\text{min}} = 2s_\phi$. The full leapfrog potential keeps the analytic terms verbatim,

$$\Phi_\theta(\mathbf{q}) = \underbrace{-\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{q}}_{\text{LP drift}} + \Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}(\mathbf{q}) + \rho_{\text{box}} B_{\text{box}}(\mathbf{q}) + \rho_{\text{cap}} B_{\text{cap}}(\mathbf{q}), \quad (39)$$

with box and capacity log-barriers $B_{\text{box}}(\mathbf{q}) = -\sum_i [\log q_i + \log(1 - q_i)]$ and $B_{\text{cap}}(\mathbf{q}) = -\log(C - \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{q})$.

a) *Why the quadratic well, not a bump.*: The separable bump $s_\phi \sum_i a_i q_i(1 - q_i)$, a natural first choice, is *inert at the vertices*: $q_i(1 - q_i) \equiv 0$ for $q_i \in \{0, 1\}$ and its derivative $a_i(1 - 2q_i)$ has fixed sign independent of any learned target. On the binary contour shells of Section G-C it contributes neither energy nor force across decided coordinates and therefore cannot be ranked. The quadratic well $(q_i - t_i)^2$ is *binary-discriminative* (its value at a vertex depends on t_i), pulls a coordinate toward *either* vertex, has nonzero force at $\{0, 1\}$, and is the only separable form whose $\nabla_{\mathbf{q}}^2$ is a genuine basin. The $\gamma \|\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{t}\|^2$ anchor is an effective room-closing term; here \mathbf{t} is predicted from features, so it must generalize. The basin strength is initialized at $s_\phi \approx 0.05\text{--}0.1$ rather than near 10^{-3} : a near-zero anchor cannot influence $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}$, so the shooting loss cannot train \mathbf{t} , a coupling that must be broken by a moderate initial s_ϕ . The basin floor self-balances down to 0 where there is no room.

B. Learned Riemannian metric with an $O(n)$ inverse

The kinetic energy is $\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{p}^\top M_\theta(\mathbf{q})^{-1} \mathbf{p}$. The learned metric keeps the analytic Sherman–Morrison rank-1 structure $M_\theta(\mathbf{q}) = D_\theta(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{u}_\theta \mathbf{u}_\theta^\top$, with both the diagonal and the rank-1 term scaled by feature-predicted, scale-invariant multipliers:

$$D_\theta(\mathbf{q})_{ii} = \rho_{\text{box}} \left(\frac{1}{q_i^2} + \frac{1}{(1 - q_i)^2} \right) m_i,$$

$$m_i = \text{softplus}(H_i W_m + b_m) (\approx 1 \text{ at init}), \quad (40)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_\theta = g_u \sqrt{\rho_{\text{cap}} \alpha_{\text{cap}}(\mathbf{q})} \mathbf{w},$$

$$\alpha_{\text{cap}}(\mathbf{q}) = \frac{1}{(C - \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{q})^2},$$

$$g_u = \text{softplus}(b_{g_u}) (\approx 1). \quad (41)$$

The leapfrog never forms M_θ ; it applies the inverse via Sherman–Morrison in $O(n)$:

$$M_\theta^{-1} \mathbf{p} = D_\theta^{-1} \mathbf{p} - \frac{\mathbf{u}_\theta^\top D_\theta^{-1} \mathbf{p}}{1 + \mathbf{u}_\theta^\top D_\theta^{-1} \mathbf{u}_\theta} D_\theta^{-1} \mathbf{u}_\theta. \quad (42)$$

At $m_i \equiv 1$, $g_u \equiv 1$ this reduces *exactly* to the analytic metric M of Section IX, so the learned flow is a continuous deformation of the fixed one. The discrete update is the same damped primal–dual leapfrog ($k_{\text{leap}}=16$ steps, $h=0.02$, damping $\gamma=0.97$ multiplying both momenta each step, so that *lower γ means more damping, hence less travel*), with position half-step $\mathbf{q} \leftarrow \mathbf{q} + h M_\theta(\mathbf{q})^{-1} \mathbf{p}_q$ and force $\nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \Phi_\theta = \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} V_{\text{LP+barrier}} + 2s_\phi(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{t})$.

C. The ΔV -contour rank loss and the basin loss

Supervision comes from *value level-set contours*. From each oracle \mathbf{x}^* , the L-move ladder walks outward by worsening 2-swaps to produce shells $\mathbf{x}_{\delta_0} = \mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{x}_{\delta_1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{\delta_R}$ at increasing *relative value gaps* $\Delta \bar{V}_k = (z^* - z(\mathbf{x}_{\delta_k}))/z^*$. The rank loss requires Φ_θ^{res} to increase outward by a margin proportional to the relative-gap increment:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{rank}} = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{k=1}^R \left[\Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}(\mathbf{x}_{\delta_{k-1}}) + m_{\text{swap}} (\widetilde{\Delta V}_k - \widetilde{\Delta V}_{k-1}) - \Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}(\mathbf{x}_{\delta_k}) \right]_+ \quad (43)$$

a) *Why ranking the full potential Φ_θ is inert.*: The shells are *value level-sets by definition*, so $-\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{x}$ orders them perfectly and trivially, and its raw inter-shell gap (thousands) swamps the relative margin $m_{\text{swap}} \widetilde{\Delta V} \leq 0.1$. The hinge on $\Phi_\theta = -\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{x} + \Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}$ is then satisfied with enormous slack, is identically zero, and back-propagates no gradient to Φ_θ^{res} (empirically $\mathcal{L}_{\text{rank}} = 0.0000$ every step). Ranking Φ_θ^{res} *alone* forces the learned anchor \mathbf{t} to carry the depth ordering: configurations closer to OPT must sit closer to \mathbf{t} . The gradient is live even at the uninformative initialization $\mathbf{t} \approx \frac{1}{2}$,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_{\text{rank}}}{\partial t_i} = -2 s_\phi (x_{\text{in},i} - x_{\text{out},i})$$

on items swapped between consecutive rungs, (44)

raising t_i for items in the inner (closer-to-OPT) shell. The loss is *self-balancing and one-sided in n* : it vanishes where contours are degenerate (no room, $\mathbf{x}_{\delta_k} \approx \mathbf{x}^*$), and since room concentrates at small n in this corpus it measurably shrinks $0.0011 \rightarrow 0.00005 \rightarrow 0.00001 \rightarrow 0$ across $n \in \{50, 200, 500, 1000\}$. Because it uses relative $\widetilde{\Delta V}$, the $1/R$ average, and Φ_θ^{res} *differences* over $O(1)$ -Hamming consecutive rungs, it is $O(1)$ by construction and can only shrink, never blow up; the scale-invariance gate is therefore one-sided (fail only on growth $> 2\times$).

b) *Basin loss.*: The optimum is pinned as a stationary point with positive curvature:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{basin}} = \frac{1}{n} \left\| \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \Phi_\theta(\mathbf{x}^*) \right\|^2 + [m_0 - \lambda_{\min}(\nabla_{\mathbf{q}}^2 \Phi_\theta^{\text{res}})]_+, \quad (45)$$

where, since $\Phi_\theta = -\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{q} + \Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \Phi_\theta(\mathbf{x}^*) &= -\mathbf{v} + 2 s_\phi (\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{t}), \\ \lambda_{\min}(\nabla_{\mathbf{q}}^2 \Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}) &= 2 s_\phi. \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

Stationarity demands the anchor cancel the value drift at OPT: $2s_\phi(\mathbf{x}^* - \mathbf{t}) \approx \mathbf{v}$. The PSD term needs no Hessian autodiff, since it is the closed-form $\lambda_{\min} = 2s_\phi$ of (38), and pushes $s_\phi \geq m_0/2$.

D. The contrastive term: the LP optimum as a high-energy negative

Early runs found that nothing penalized the fractional LP optimum $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$, so the anchor \mathbf{t} could amortize toward it and Φ_θ^{res}

deepened the LP basin rather than the integer one. The fix makes $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ (ratio-greedy: 1s, one fractional break item j^* , 0s, oracle-free) an explicit high-energy negative that must rank above the integer OPT by the LP value advantage:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{contrast}} = \left[\Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}(\lfloor \mathbf{x}^* \rfloor) + m_{\text{swap}} \cdot \text{gap}_{\text{val}} - \Phi_\theta^{\text{res}}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}) \right]_+, \quad (47)$$

$$\text{gap}_{\text{val}} = [\mathbf{v}^\top \bar{\mathbf{x}} - \mathbf{v}^\top \lfloor \mathbf{x}^* \rfloor]_+ \geq 0. \quad (48)$$

It is folded into the rank term (weight w_{contrast} , default OFF) and active only when $\text{room} > 0$. Because $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is oracle-free there is nothing to memorize, so the basin-deepening *generalizes*: on held-out validation it raised $\Delta E = E(\bar{\mathbf{x}}) - E(\text{OPT})$ to $+0.078$ (78% OPT-basin) at $n=50$ and $+0.444$ (94%) at $n=200$, and repaired the no-contrastive overfit (which collapsed to $\Delta E = -0.15$, 25%).

E. Core-restricted tail-REINFORCE

We distinguish two configurations of the learned-landscape model, used by name in the tables. LEARNED-LANDSCAPE is trained by the objective of Eq. (52) above and evaluated with the standard CVaR decode. LEARNED-LANDSCAPE-R keeps that configuration and adds the core-restricted tail-REINFORCE term of this subsection, training the encoder for the deployed Monte-Carlo decoder.

The deployed decoder samples Bernoulli roundings on a reduced-cost core, so the encoder is trained for that decoder via a score-function surrogate. For $\mathbf{x} \sim \prod_i \text{Bern}(q_i)$ with reward $R(\mathbf{x}) = \text{value}(\text{repair}(\mathbf{x}))/z^*$, the estimator $\hat{g} = (R - b) \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \log p(\mathbf{x} | \mathbf{q})$ has $\partial \log p / \partial q_i = (x_i - q_i) / (q_i(1 - q_i))$, so $\text{Var}(\hat{g}) = \sum_i \text{Var}(\hat{g}_i) = \Theta(n_{\text{active}})$. With all n coordinates sampled, the signal on the $\sim 5\text{--}20$ OPT-relevant items is swamped by $O(n)$ noise, the full- n ‘‘dominant sweep’’ that forces the reinforcement weight w_{re} to zero in the learned-landscape objective.

a) *Fix: freeze the confident set, sample only the core.*: Let $\mathcal{C}_{\text{core}}$ be the $K_{\text{core}} = \text{clip}(\text{round}(\text{frac} \cdot n), \text{floor}, n)$ smallest-reduced-cost items ($\bar{c}_i = |v_i - \lambda_{\text{raw}} w_i|$, with $\lambda_{\text{raw}} = v_{j^*} / w_{j^*}$ the break ratio). Freeze every $i \notin \mathcal{C}_{\text{core}}$ to its LP-integer value \bar{x}_i in every sample, and form the log-probability over the core only:

$$x_i = \begin{cases} \mathbf{1}[u_i < q_i], & i \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{core}} \\ \bar{x}_i, & i \notin \mathcal{C}_{\text{core}} \end{cases} \quad (49)$$

$$\log p(\mathbf{x} | \mathbf{q}) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{core}}} [x_i \log q_i + (1 - x_i) \log(1 - q_i)]. \quad (50)$$

Frozen coordinates are constants, hence $\partial \log p / \partial q_i = 0$ for $i \notin \mathcal{C}_{\text{core}}$, so \hat{g} is supported on $\mathcal{C}_{\text{core}}$ and $\text{Var}(\hat{g}) = \Theta(K_{\text{core}})$, a $K_{\text{core}}/n = \text{frac}$ variance reduction ($5\times$ at 20%). The gradient concentrates on exactly the LP-uncertain items where OPT and Dantzig disagree. Setting $\text{frac}=0$ (core all-ones) recovers full- n REINFORCE backward-identically, so this strictly generalizes it. The advantage uses either a self-critical greedy baseline ($\beta=0$, $A = R - R(\text{greedy}(\mathbf{q}))$) or the risk-seeking CVaR/superquantile tail ($\beta>0$, $\eta = \text{empirical } \beta$ -

quantile of R , $A = [R - \eta]_+ / (1 - \beta)$, only the top- $(1 - \beta)$ samples carrying gradient), giving the surrogate

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{re}} = -\frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M A_m \log p(\mathbf{x}_m | \mathbf{q}). \quad (51)$$

b) Train-infer consistency.: Because the gradient trains \mathbf{q} on the core with non-core frozen to LP-integer, inference must present the same conditioning: the encoder runs on the *whole* instance to obtain $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}$, then MC decodes the core with non-core frozen (sample \rightarrow repair \rightarrow keep best incumbent \rightarrow CEM-move \mathbf{q} on the core only), *not* peel-then-encode. This is in-distribution for n in the trained range; for OOD n (e.g. P600 at $n=20,000$) encoder-on-full is OOD and peel-then-encode remains. The MC budget tracks core combinatorics, $M = \text{clip}(\alpha K_{\text{core}}, M_{\text{floor}}, M_{\text{cap}})$ ($\alpha \in \{8, 32\}$, $M_{\text{floor}}=256$, $M_{\text{cap}}=8192$, keeping decode cost $O(M_{\text{cap}} n) = O(n)$); the core fraction stays fixed for apples-to-apples.

c) Adaptive on/off gate.: Rather than a fixed warmup/ramp, w_{re} is EMA-toggled by the kinetics loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{kin}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{shoot}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{move}}^{\text{OPT}}$: turn reinforce *on* when \mathcal{L}_{kin} plateaus (no improvement $> \varepsilon$ for ≥ 8 evaluations, after a minimum step), and *off* when the loss spikes $> 1.25 \times$ the reference (variance) or the step blows up. The weight is smoothed $w_{\text{re}} \leftarrow 0.95 w_{\text{re}} + 0.05 (W_{\text{re}} \cdot [\text{on}])$ so toggles ramp over ~ 200 steps.

F. The full objective

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = & \underbrace{w_{\text{shoot}} \|\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}} - \mathbf{x}^*\|^2}_{\text{geodesic shooting}} \\ & + \underbrace{w_{\text{rank}} (\mathcal{L}_{\text{rank}} + w_{\text{contrast}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{contrast}})}_{\text{contour rank } (\Phi_{\theta}^{\text{res}}) + \text{LP-negative}} \\ & + \underbrace{w_{\text{basin}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{basin}}}_{\text{OPT stationary} + \text{PSD}} \\ & + \underbrace{w_{\text{band}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{SWBM}} + w_{\text{move}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{move}}^{\text{OPT}}}_{\text{focal margin} + \text{move-optimality}} \\ & + \underbrace{w_{\text{re}}(t) \mathcal{L}_{\text{re}} + w_{\text{kkt}} \rho}_{\text{core-restricted REINFORCE} + \text{KKT feasibility}} \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

Defaults: $w_{\text{shoot}}=1$, $w_{\text{rank}}=0.3$, $w_{\text{basin}}=0.1$, $w_{\text{band}}=1$, $w_{\text{move}}=0.5$, $w_{\text{re}}=0.5$, $w_{\text{kkt}}=0.01$, tail level $\beta=0.8$. The objective is minimized by a Lookahead-wrapped AdamW optimizer with a warmup-cosine learning-rate schedule; Appendix I records the remaining optimizer and numerical-precision settings. The fixed-LP control is recovered exactly by $w_{\text{rank}}=w_{\text{basin}}=0$ with the residual potential and metric frozen (identical to the fixed-LP flow of Section IX).

G. Preliminary findings

- **The basin is solved and generalizes.** The contrastive term (48) makes the integer OPT a deeper energy basin than the LP optimum, validated on *held-out* data ($\Delta E > 0$ for

78%/94% of $n=50/200$; $\cos(-\nabla E|_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}}, \mathbf{x}^* - \bar{\mathbf{x}}) > 0$ for 100%). Because $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ is oracle-free, nothing is memorized.

- **The flow lands a few items off OPT, robustly.** OPT is low-energy but *not stationary* ($\|\nabla_{\mathbf{q}} \Phi_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}^*)\| \approx \|\mathbf{v}\|$: the $-\mathbf{v}$ pull dominates and the anchor barely dents it, per (46)). The damped flow settles at the interior LP fixed point a small, roughly constant number of items from OPT, the integrality-gap wall, and kinetics sweeps do not move it. The learned anchor \mathbf{t} is therefore a good *discriminator* of depth but not a *guide* to OPT.
- **The productive lever is a core-restricted decoder, not more flow.** Training the encoder for the deployed Monte-Carlo decoder via core-restricted tail-REINFORCE (51) (LEARNED-LANDSCAPE-R) is, among the q -sources sharing the dynamic core-restricted decode of Table VI, the best on the out-of-distribution P600 core (133/627 exact, ahead of uniform 95, ratio-softmax 101, and greedy 111).

This dynamic core-restricted decode differs from the fixed reduced-cost peel of the main text, under which the structured-gradient encoders close more on the *same* P600 pool (SWAP-BAND 209, L-MOVE 173; Table II). The two are therefore not cross-comparable, and a full per-instance evaluation of both decodes on a single basis is left to future work.

APPENDIX H

AN xLSTM-MOE SEQUENCE ENCODER (NEGATIVE RESULT)

Before adopting the permutation-equivariant set encoder and the fixed Hamiltonian flow of Section IX, we tried a classic sequence-model encoder in the spirit of language-model architectures: a bidirectional mLSTM [59] that consumes items as an ordered sequence and emits a per-item score $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^n$. It did not improve on the set encoder, and ordering the items forfeits the permutation equivariance of the exchangeable item set, so we did not adopt it. The one contribution worth keeping is in engineering rather than accuracy: the $\mathcal{O}(\log n)$ parallel-scan reformulation of Appendix H-B is, to our knowledge, a novel parallelization of the bidirectional mLSTM recurrence. We record the construction here as a documented negative result. Throughout this appendix, σ denotes this legacy sequence-encoder score and plays the role taken by the kinetics $(\mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{p}_0, \lambda_0)$ in the main text; it is unrelated to the analytic (p, k) score $\sigma_j^{(p,k)}$ of Section III.

A. Bidirectional mLSTM cell

We use a bidirectional mLSTM [59] as the per-item encoder. Items are presented in decreasing Dantzig ratio v_j/w_j , with deterministic tie-breaking. The learned score produced by the encoder is denoted by σ_j and is used only after this encoding step.

TABLE VI: Learned landscape, dynamic core-restricted decode (encoder-on-full \rightarrow 20% reduced-cost core \rightarrow CVaR- $\beta=0.8$, $r=4$ Monte-Carlo with $M=\text{clip}(32K_{\text{core}}, 256, 8192)$), the *same* decode applied to every q -source, scored over the full set (Jookan 2975, P600 627). “closed” counts exact-OPT incumbents; “gap%” is the mean relative gap. LEARNED-LANDSCAPE-R is the learned-landscape encoder of Section G trained with the core-restricted tail-REINFORCE; “greedy” decodes its $\mathbf{q}_{k_{\text{leap}}}$ without Monte-Carlo. *Note*: this decoder differs from the fixed core peel of Table II, so closures are not cross-comparable across the two tables. Among the q -sources sharing this decode, LEARNED-LANDSCAPE-R is the best on the out-of-distribution P600 set (133 exact, 0.13% gap; vs uniform 95, ratio-softmax 101, greedy 111); in-distribution the peel already does most of the work (greedy alone reaches 951 exact on Jookan), so the q -sources are comparable there. We also evaluated the no-REINFORCE variant (122 exact on P600) and larger, smaller, and fixed-versus-dynamic cores; all work, with LEARNED-LANDSCAPE-R the strongest and a superset (a zero core fraction recovers the no-REINFORCE estimator).

q -source	Jookan (2975)		P600 (627)	
	closed	gap%	closed	gap%
greedy ($q_{k_{\text{leap}}}$, no MC)	951	1.37	111	1.33
uniform	373	0.24	95	0.86
ratio_softmax	470	0.17	101	0.26
LEARNED-LANDSCAPE-R	467	0.25	133	0.13

With per-step input $\mathbf{x}_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the mLSTM cell is

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{q}_t, \mathbf{k}_t, \mathbf{u}_t &= \mathbf{W}_q \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{W}_k \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{W}_u \mathbf{x}_t, \\
i_t &= \exp(\min\{\mathbf{w}_i^\top \mathbf{x}_t + b_i, 5\}), \\
f_t &= \varsigma(\mathbf{w}_f^\top \mathbf{x}_t + b_f), \\
\mathbf{o}_t &= \varsigma(\mathbf{W}_o \mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_o), \\
\mathbf{M}_t &= f_t \mathbf{M}_{t-1} + i_t \mathbf{u}_t \mathbf{k}_t^\top, \\
\mathbf{n}_t &= f_t \mathbf{n}_{t-1} + i_t \mathbf{k}_t, \\
\mathbf{h}_t &= \mathbf{o}_t \odot \frac{\mathbf{M}_t \mathbf{q}_t}{\max(|\mathbf{n}_t^\top \mathbf{q}_t|, 1)}.
\end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

Here $\varsigma(\cdot)$ denotes the logistic sigmoid; we write it as ς rather than σ to avoid clashing with the per-item score σ_j . Here $\mathbf{q}_t, \mathbf{k}_t, \mathbf{u}_t, \mathbf{n}_t, \mathbf{h}_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\mathbf{M}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$. We run the cell once in Dantzig-ratio order and once in the reverse order, concatenate the two hidden states, and project the result to a scalar score σ_j . For fixed hidden width d , the encoder has $\mathcal{O}(n d^2)$ total work and $\mathcal{O}(d^2)$ recurrent state.

B. Parallel-scan reformulation

The two recurrent states in Eq. (53) have the same affine recurrence. We define

$$\mathbf{S}_t := (\mathbf{M}_t, \mathbf{n}_t), \quad \mathbf{b}_t := (i_t \mathbf{u}_t \mathbf{k}_t^\top, i_t \mathbf{k}_t). \tag{54}$$

Then

$$\mathbf{S}_t = f_t \mathbf{S}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_t. \tag{55}$$

A block with decay a and increment \mathbf{b} maps \mathbf{S} to $a\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{b}$. If a left block (a_L, \mathbf{b}_L) is followed by a right block (a_R, \mathbf{b}_R) , the combined block is

$$(a_R a_L, a_R \mathbf{b}_L + \mathbf{b}_R). \tag{56}$$

This composition is associative. Therefore, an associative scan [60] computes all states $\{(\mathbf{M}_t, \mathbf{n}_t)\}_{t=1}^n$ in $\mathcal{O}(\log n)$ parallel depth and $\mathcal{O}(n d^2)$ total work.

We verify the scan implementation against the sequential recurrence. In double precision with random parameters, the maximum relative error is between 10^{-14} and 10^{-12} for $n \in \{64, 200, 1000, 5000\}$. In single precision with trained

parameters at $n \in \{200, 1000, 5000, 20000\}$, the Spearman rank correlation between sequential and scan scores is at least 0.99997. The decoded argmax and beam selections are identical in all validation runs.

C. Mixture of experts (union ensemble)

The mixture-of-experts head below was dropped in the final pipeline; we record it for completeness as part of this negative result. A single multi-family expert does not perform equally well on all hard families. We therefore use a union ensemble with two groups:

- **Group A:** $N_A = 2$ multi-family generalists with hidden width $d = 32$, trained on all six families with a curriculum $n \in \{200, 500, 1000\}$.
- **Group B:** $N_B = 5$ per-family specialists with hidden width $d = 16$, one each for *SimilarWeightsUncorrelated*, *CubeFit*, *Weakly*, *Uncorrelated*, and *QuadFit*. An *AlmostStrong* specialist did not win on any validation instance in preliminary cross-validation, so we omit it.

The two groups have different hidden widths and are evaluated as two separate batched ensembles. Each expert produces a score vector $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, which is decoded by capacity-respecting greedy selection. The candidate pool is the union of all decoded expert selections together with Dantzig’s greedy solution \mathbf{x}^{Dant} .

Different benchmark families can favor different scoring rules, so we combine generalists and family-specific specialists rather than relying on a single encoder. The ensemble design is empirical but consistent with the distribution-dependent picture of Theorem 1.

D. Pairwise crossover on the disagreement core

The crossover step below is a special-case decoder; the Monte-Carlo and CVaR tail-refine decoders of Section IX subsume it and apply to any 0–1 MIP with inequality constraints. Given the candidate pool, let $A, B \in \{0, 1\}^n$ be the

two highest-value distinct feasible selections. If all candidates coincide, we return that selection. Otherwise define

$$\begin{aligned} F &:= \{i : A_i = B_i = 1\}, \\ D &:= \{i : A_i \neq B_i\}, \\ C_D &:= C - \sum_{i \in F} w_i. \end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

We refine the candidate pool by solving the exact 0–1 subproblem on the items in D with residual capacity C_D . The dynamic program stores only nondominated weight–value states rather than an array of length C_D . Let $\hat{D} \subseteq D$ be the subset returned by the dynamic program; the final selection is $F \cup \hat{D}$.

Proposition 13 (Crossover monotonicity). *The crossover solution satisfies $z(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) \geq \max\{z(A), z(B)\}$.*

Proof. Both A and B contain all items in F . Their restrictions to the disagreement set D are feasible for the residual capacity C_D , because A and B are feasible for the original capacity. The dynamic program optimizes over all feasible subsets of D , so it can recover at least the better of these two restrictions. Adding the common value of the items in F gives the claim. \square

The set D contains exactly the items on which the two best candidates disagree. It is therefore a data-dependent reduced core. Instead of searching all items, we search only the exchange choices exposed by the two strongest candidates. This refinement does not claim to solve the full instance exactly, because items rejected by both candidates remain fixed to zero. Its purpose is to improve the candidate pool while guaranteeing that the final value is never below the better of A and B .

Empirically, $|D| \ll n$, often by two orders of magnitude, so this exact refinement is inexpensive. A sequential 5-way crossover over the top five candidates gives the same selected solutions as the 2-way version on both the Pisinger $n = 20,000$ corpus and the Jookan $n = 1,200$ corpus. Thus, on these benchmarks, the second-best candidate already exposes the useful exchange set.

E. Verdict

Despite the favorable parallel-scan complexity, the sequence-model encoder did not improve over the permutation-equivariant set encoder of Section IX on the hard corpora, and the imposed item ordering forfeits the permutation equivariance that an exchangeable item set makes available. We therefore adopt the set encoder and the fixed Hamiltonian flow in the main text, and keep this construction as a documented negative result whose parallel-scan reformulation may nonetheless be of independent interest.

APPENDIX I IMPLEMENTATION NOTES

A. JAX implementation

The pipeline is implemented in JAX. Inference and a training step are each expressed as a single fused just-in-time-compiled function, so the encoder forward pass, the fixed leapfrog rollout, the reduced-cost peel, and the optimizer update execute in one

TABLE VII: Cold-call and warm-call latency for the full pipeline at capacity $C = 10^{10}$. The cold call includes trace, compile, and one run. Warm-call statistics are computed over five repeated invocations of the same instance from the JIT cache. Returned objective values are bit-identical across calls; the $p_{10}-p_{90}$ spread is below 5% of the median.

n	cold	warm	compile
1,000	10.06 s	36.9 ± 1.0 ms	≈ 10.0 s
1,200	12.60 s	43.0 ± 0.9 ms	≈ 12.6 s

traced program. To keep traced shapes static and avoid the compile blow-up of indexed scatter under batched vectorization, all index operations are written as gathers rather than in-place scatters. The encoder and the symplectic flow are evaluated in double precision (`float64`), which the ISAB attention maps and the Sherman–Morrison metric inverse require for the permutation-equivariance and KKT-residual diagnostics to hold to 10^{-14} . The objective of Eq. (52) is minimized with a Lookahead wrapper around AdamW (weight decay 10^{-4} , $\varepsilon=10^{-6}$) applied after clip-by-global-norm at threshold 1, under a warmup-cosine learning-rate schedule.

B. JIT compilation and warm-call timing

The set encoder, the fixed leapfrog rollout, the reduced-cost peel, and the CVaR decode are wrapped in a single just-in-time-compiled function whose traced shapes depend on the sequence length n . The first call at a new value of n therefore incurs trace and compile time. Subsequent calls at the same shape use the cached executable. Table VII reports the corresponding cold- and warm-call timings for the full pipeline (Section XI-B). The cold-call runtime includes trace, compile, and one full pipeline run. Warm calls are repeated invocations from the JIT cache. In all repeats, the returned objective value is bit-identical.

The compile cost is paid once per sequence length and is amortized over subsequent instances with the same traced shape. The per-instance decode latencies reported in Table III (Section XI-B) are computed from warm calls, with the first-call compile outlier dropped.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. H. Papadimitriou and K. Steiglitz, *Combinatorial Optimization: Algorithms and Complexity*. North Chelmsford, MA, USA: Courier Corporation, 1998.
- [2] B. Korte and J. Vygen, *Combinatorial Optimization: Theory and Algorithms*. Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 6 ed., 2018.
- [3] R. M. Karp, "Reducibility among combinatorial problems," in *Complexity of Computer Computations* (R. E. Miller, J. W. Thatcher, and J. D. Bohlinger, eds.), pp. 85–103, New York, NY, USA: Plenum Press, 1972.
- [4] C. Li, Z. Gan, Z. Yang, J. Yang, L. Li, L. Wang, and J. Gao, "Multimodal foundation models: From specialists to general-purpose assistants," *Foundations and Trends in Computer Graphics and Vision*, vol. 16, no. 1-2, pp. 1–214, 2024.
- [5] F. Guo, R. Guan, Y. Li, Q. Liu, X. Wang, C. Yang, and J. Wang, "Foundation models in bioinformatics," *National Science Review*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. nwaf028, 2025.
- [6] J. Lee, Y. Lee, J. Kim, A. R. Kosiorek, S. Choi, and Y. W. Teh, "Set Transformer: A Framework for Attention-based Permutation-Invariant Neural Networks," in *Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML 2019, 9-15 June 2019, Long Beach, California, USA* (K. Chaudhuri and R. Salakhutdinov, eds.), vol. 97 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pp. 3744–3753, PMLR, 2019.
- [7] K. Smith, M. Palaniswami, and M. Krishnamoorthy, "Neural techniques for combinatorial optimization with applications," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 1301–1318, 1998.
- [8] I. Bello, H. Pham, Q. V. Le, M. Norouzi, and S. Bengio, "Neural Combinatorial Optimization with Reinforcement Learning," in *5th International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2017, Toulon, France, April 24-26, 2017, Workshop Track Proceedings*, OpenReview.net, 2017.
- [9] W. Kool, H. van Hoof, and M. Welling, "Attention, Learn to Solve Routing Problems!," in *7th International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2019, New Orleans, LA, USA, May 6-9, 2019*, OpenReview.net, 2019.
- [10] E. B. Khalil, H. Dai, Y. Zhang, B. Dilkina, and L. Song, "Learning Combinatorial Optimization Algorithms over Graphs," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 30: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2017, December 4-9, 2017, Long Beach, CA, USA* (I. Guyon, U. von Luxburg, S. Bengio, H. M. Wallach, R. Fergus, S. V. N. Vishwanathan, and R. Garnett, eds.), pp. 6348–6358, 2017.
- [11] Y. Kwon, J. Choo, B. Kim, I. Yoon, Y. Gwon, and S. Min, "POMO: policy optimization with multiple optima for reinforcement learning," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 33: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2020, NeurIPS 2020, December 6-12, 2020, virtual* (H. Larochelle, M. Ranzato, R. Hadsell, M. Balcan, and H. Lin, eds.), 2020.
- [12] Y. Bengio, A. Lodi, and A. Prouvost, "Machine Learning for Combinatorial Optimization: A Methodological Tour d'Horizon," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 290, no. 2, pp. 405–421, 2021.
- [13] N. Mazyavkina, S. Sviridov, S. Ivanov, and E. Burnaev, "Reinforcement learning for combinatorial optimization: A survey," *Computers & Operations Research*, vol. 134, p. 105400, 2021.
- [14] R. Qiu, Z. Sun, and Y. Yang, "DIMES: A Differentiable Meta Solver for Combinatorial Optimization Problems," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 35: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2022, NeurIPS 2022, New Orleans, LA, USA, November 28 - December 9, 2022* (S. Koyejo, S. Mohamed, A. Agarwal, D. Belgrave, K. Cho, and A. Oh, eds.), 2022.
- [15] Z. Zhang, Z. Wu, H. Zhang, and J. Wang, "Meta-learning-based deep reinforcement learning for multiobjective optimization problems," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 7978–7991, 2022.
- [16] Z. Sun and Y. Yang, "DIFUSCO: Graph-based Diffusion Solvers for Combinatorial Optimization," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 36: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2023, NeurIPS 2023, New Orleans, LA, USA, December 10 - 16, 2023* (A. Oh, T. Naumann, A. Globerson, K. Saenko, M. Hardt, and S. Levine, eds.), 2023.
- [17] Q. Cappart, D. Chételat, E. B. Khalil, A. Lodi, C. Morris, and P. Veličković, "Combinatorial Optimization and Reasoning with Graph Neural Networks," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 24, no. 130, pp. 1–61, 2023.
- [18] A. H. C. Correia, D. E. Worrall, and R. Bondesan, "Neural simulated annealing," in *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics, 25-27 April 2023, Palau de Congressos, Valencia, Spain* (F. J. R. Ruiz, J. G. Dy, and J. van de Meent, eds.), *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pp. 4946–4962, PMLR, 2023.
- [19] H. A. Nomer, K. A. Alnowibet, A. Elsayed, and A. W. Mohamed, "Neural Knapsack: A Neural Network Based Solver for the Knapsack Problem," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 224200–224210, 2020.
- [20] S. Požgaj, D. Georgiev, M. Šilić, and P. Veličković, "KNARsack: Teaching neural algorithmic reasoners to solve pseudo-polynomial problems," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2509.15239*, 2025.
- [21] D. Pisinger, "Where are the hard knapsack problems?," *Computers & Operations Research*, vol. 32, no. 9, pp. 2271–2284, 2005.
- [22] K. Smith-Miles, J. Christiansen, and M. A. Muñoz, "Revisiting where are the hard knapsack problems? via instance space analysis," *Computers & Operations Research*, vol. 128, p. 105184, 2021.
- [23] J. Jookan, P. Leyman, and P. De Causmaecker, "A new class of hard problem instances for the 0–1 knapsack problem," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 301, no. 3, pp. 841–854, 2022.
- [24] H. Kellerer, U. Pferschy, and D. Pisinger, *Knapsack Problems*. Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2004.
- [25] V. Chvátal, "Hard knapsack problems," *Operations Research*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 1402–1411, 1980.
- [26] B. Hunsaker and C. A. Tovey, "Simple lifted cover inequalities and hard knapsack problems," *Discrete Optimization*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 219–228, 2005.
- [27] Stanford Center for Research on Foundation Models, "Reflections on foundation models." <https://hai.stanford.edu/news/reflections-foundation-models>, Oct. 2021. Accessed: 2026-05-27.
- [28] S. Martello, D. Pisinger, and P. Toth, "Dynamic Programming and Strong Bounds for the 0-1 Knapsack Problem," *Management Science*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 414–424, 1999.
- [29] R. da Silva, T. A. de Queiroz, and R. C. S. Schouery, "RECORD: a state-of-the-art exact solver for the 0–1 knapsack problem," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2604.05232*, 2026.
- [30] A. H. G. Rinnooy Kan, L. Stougie, and C. Vercellis, "A class of generalized greedy algorithms for the multi-knapsack problem," *Discrete Applied Mathematics*, vol. 42, pp. 279–290, 1993.
- [31] R. Beier and B. Vöcking, "Random knapsack in expected polynomial time," in *Proceedings of the Thirty-Fifth Annual ACM Symposium on Theory of Computing*, pp. 232–241, 2003.
- [32] R. Beier and B. Vöcking, "Probabilistic analysis of knapsack core algorithms," in *SODA*, vol. 4, pp. 468–477, 2004.
- [33] P. Yin, J. Lyu, S. Zhang, S. J. Osher, Y. Qi, and J. Xin, "Understanding straight-through estimator in training activation quantized neural nets," in *7th International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2019, New Orleans, LA, USA, May 6-9, 2019*, OpenReview.net, 2019.
- [34] G. B. Dantzig, "Discrete-Variable Extremum Problems," *Operations Research*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 266–288, 1957.
- [35] M. Blondel, O. Teboul, Q. Berthet, and J. Djolonga, "Fast differentiable sorting and ranking," in *International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*, 2020.
- [36] Q. Berthet, M. Blondel, O. Teboul, M. Cuturi, J.-P. Vert, and F. Bach, "Learning with differentiable perturbed optimizers," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (H. Larochelle, M. Ranzato, R. Hadsell, M. Balcan, and H. Lin, eds.), vol. 33, pp. 9508–9519, Curran Associates, Inc., 2020.
- [37] V. Niculae, A. F. T. Martins, M. Blondel, and C. Cardie, "SparseMAP: Differentiable sparse structured inference," in *Proceedings of the 35th International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML 2018, Stockholm, Sweden, July 10-15, 2018* (J. G. Dy and A. Krause, eds.), *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pp. 3796–3805, PMLR, 2018.
- [38] L. Böttcher, T. Asikis, and I. Fragkos, "Control of dual-sourcing inventory systems using recurrent neural networks," *INFORMS Journal on Computing*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 1308–1328, 2023.
- [39] J. J. Hopfield and D. W. Tank, "'Neural' computation of decisions in optimization problems," *Biological Cybernetics*, vol. 52, no. 3, pp. 141–152, 1985.
- [40] M. Ohlsson, C. Peterson, and B. Söderberg, "Neural networks for optimization problems with inequality constraints: the knapsack problem," *Neural Computation*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 331–339, 1993.
- [41] M. Ohlsson and H. Pi, "A study of the mean field approach to knapsack problems," *Neural Networks*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 263–271, 1997.
- [42] K. A. Smith, "Neural networks for combinatorial optimization: A review of more than a decade of research," *INFORMS Journal on Computing*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 15–34, 1999.
- [43] O. Vinyals, M. Fortunato, and N. Jaitly, "Pointer Networks," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 28: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2015, December 7-12, 2015, Montreal, Quebec, Canada* (C. Cortes, N. D. Lawrence, D. D. Lee, M. Sugiyama, and R. Garnett, eds.), pp. 2692–2700, 2015.

- [44] C. K. Joshi, T. Laurent, and X. Bresson, “An Efficient Graph Convolutional Network Technique for the Travelling Salesman Problem,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.01227*, 2019.
- [45] M. J. Schuetz, J. K. Brubaker, and H. G. Katzgraber, “Combinatorial Optimization with Physics-Inspired Graph Neural Networks,” *Nature Machine Intelligence*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 367–377, 2022.
- [46] N. Karalias and A. Loukas, “Erdős Goes Neural: An Unsupervised Learning Framework for Combinatorial Optimization on Graphs,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 33: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2020, NeurIPS 2020, December 6-12, 2020, virtual* (H. Larochelle, M. Ranzato, R. Hadsell, M. Balcan, and H. Lin, eds.), 2020.
- [47] J. Toenshoff, M. Ritzert, H. Wolf, and M. Grohe, “Graph Neural Networks for Maximum Constraint Satisfaction,” *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 3, p. 580607, 2021.
- [48] S. Boettcher, “Inability of a Graph Neural Network Heuristic to Outperform Greedy Algorithms in Solving Combinatorial Optimization Problems,” *Nature Machine Intelligence*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 24–25, 2023.
- [49] M. C. Angelini and F. Ricci-Tersenghi, “Modern Graph Neural Networks Do Worse than Classical Greedy Algorithms in Solving Combinatorial Optimization Problems Like Maximum Independent Set,” *Nature Machine Intelligence*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 29–31, 2023.
- [50] D. Gamarnik, “Barriers for the Performance of Graph Neural Networks (GNN) in Discrete Random Structures,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 120, no. 46, p. e2314092120, 2023.
- [51] C. Hertrich and M. Skutella, “Provably Good Solutions to the Knapsack Problem via Neural Networks of Bounded Size,” in *Thirty-Fifth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, AAAI 2021, Thirty-Third Conference on Innovative Applications of Artificial Intelligence, IAAI 2021, The Eleventh Symposium on Educational Advances in Artificial Intelligence, EAAI 2021, Virtual Event, February 2-9, 2021*, pp. 7685–7693, AAAI Press, 2021.
- [52] C. Hertrich and M. Skutella, “Provably Good Solutions to the Knapsack Problem via Neural Networks of Bounded Size,” *INFORMS Journal on Computing*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 1079–1097, 2023.
- [53] K. Smith-Miles, M. Muñoz, and N. Neelofar, “MATILDA: Melbourne algorithm test instance library with data analytics,” *URL: https://matilda.unimelb.edu.au*, 2019.
- [54] S. Lee and J. Park, “Dual-mode dynamics neural network (D2NN) for knapsack packing problem,” in *Proceedings of 1993 International Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN-93-Nagoya, Japan)*, vol. 3, pp. 2425–2428, 1993.
- [55] Y. Bengio, N. Léonard, and A. Courville, “Estimating or propagating gradients through stochastic neurons for conditional computation,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1308.3432*, 2013.
- [56] B. Amos and J. Z. Kolter, “OptNet: Differentiable optimization as a layer in neural networks,” in *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML 2017, Sydney, NSW, Australia, 6-11 August 2017* (D. Precup and Y. W. Teh, eds.), Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, pp. 136–145, PMLR, 2017.
- [57] A. Mensch and M. Blondel, “Differentiable dynamic programming for structured prediction and attention,” in *Proceedings of the 35th International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML 2018, Stockholm, Sweden, July 10-15, 2018* (J. G. Dy and A. Krause, eds.), Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, pp. 3459–3468, PMLR, 2018.
- [58] M. Cuturi, O. Teboul, and J. Vert, “Differentiable ranking and sorting using optimal transport,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 32: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2019, NeurIPS 2019, December 8-14, 2019, Vancouver, BC, Canada* (H. M. Wallach, H. Larochelle, A. Beygelzimer, F. d’Alché-Buc, E. B. Fox, and R. Garnett, eds.), pp. 6858–6868, 2019.
- [59] M. Beck, K. Pöppel, M. Spanring, A. Auer, O. Prudnikova, M. Kopp, G. Klambauer, J. Brandstetter, and S. Hochreiter, “xLSTM: Extended long short-term memory,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 38: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2024, NeurIPS 2024, Vancouver, BC, Canada, December 10-15, 2024* (A. Globersons, L. Mackey, D. Belgrave, A. Fan, U. Paquet, J. M. Tomczak, and C. Zhang, eds.), 2024.
- [60] G. E. Blelloch, “Prefix sums and their applications,” Tech. Rep. CMU-CS-90-190, Carnegie Mellon University, 1990.
- [61] J. T. H. Smith, A. Warrington, and S. W. Linderman, “Simplified state space layers for sequence modeling,” in *The Eleventh International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2023, Kigali, Rwanda, May 1-5, 2023*, OpenReview.net, 2023.
- [62] E. Martin and C. Cundy, “Parallelizing linear recurrent neural nets over sequence length,” in *6th International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2018, Vancouver, BC, Canada, April 30 - May 3, 2018, Conference Track Proceedings*, OpenReview.net, 2018.
- [63] D. Pisinger, “A minimal algorithm for the 0–1 knapsack problem,” *Operations Research*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 758–767, 1997.
- [64] A. V. Goldberg and A. Marchetti-Spaccamela, “On finding the exact solution of a zero-one knapsack problem,” in *Proceedings of the 16th Annual ACM Symposium on Theory of Computing, April 30 - May 2, 1984, Washington, DC, USA* (R. A. DeMillo, ed.), pp. 359–368, ACM, 1984.
- [65] C. J. Maddison, D. Paulin, Y. W. Teh, B. O’Donoghue, and A. Doucet, “Hamiltonian descent methods,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1809.05042*, 2018.
- [66] A. Cherukuri, E. Mallada, and J. Cortés, “Asymptotic convergence of constrained primal–dual dynamics,” *Systems & Control Letters*, vol. 87, pp. 10–15, 2016.
- [67] E. Hairer, C. Lubich, and G. Wanner, *Geometric Numerical Integration: Structure-Preserving Algorithms for Ordinary Differential Equations*, vol. 31 of *Springer Series in Computational Mathematics*. Springer, 2 ed., 2006.
- [68] D. P. Bertsekas, *Constrained Optimization and Lagrange Multiplier Methods*. New York: Academic Press, 1982.
- [69] R. J. Williams, “Simple statistical gradient-following algorithms for connectionist reinforcement learning,” *Machine Learning*, vol. 8, no. 3–4, pp. 229–256, 1992.
- [70] S. J. Rennie, E. Marcheret, Y. Mroueh, J. Ross, and V. Goel, “Self-critical sequence training for image captioning,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pp. 7008–7024, 2017.
- [71] R. T. Rockafellar and S. Uryasev, “Optimization of conditional value-at-risk,” *Journal of Risk*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 21–42, 2000.